

Deliverable D4.6

Report on IQS, Services Integration and deployment

Deliverable report

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DIGIECOQUARRY project is fully concerned about the potential social risks that may arise as a consequence of the project's activities. For this reason, a dedicated Work Package (**WP7 - Mechanisms for social acceptance & interaction with policymakers**) is active since the beginning of the project identifying, analyzing and monitoring social risks in each of the project sites. Main social risks have been already analyzed and classified in deliverables 7.1 and 7.2, including also potential risks of DIGIECOQUARRY technologies' deployment beyond the end of the project. The identification and classification of social risks allow **a close follow-up of the main potential negative impacts in society to avoid them throughout the whole project activities**. Among potential social risks, the impact on the workforce is monitored with specific attention to ensure full adaptation of workers to new working technologies and processes and avoid job destruction.

Withing the aim of WP4, it is important to consider the data collected from the workers to develop and validate advanced algorithms and models to optimize quarry processes and make them more sustainable. By taking into account the data collected, related to social risks and the quarry workers, we can develop more accurate and effective models that reflect the actual working conditions and ensure that the solutions implemented are adapted to their needs.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
BI	Business Intelligence
BIM	Building Information Modelling
BMT	Business Management tools
CDE	Common Data Environment
CDMP	Centralized Data Management Platform for DEQ
CPU	Central Processing Unit
D2M	Drill-to-Mill
DEQ	DIGIECOQUARRY
DIU	Data Interface Unit
EDM	Environmental Data Management
EMT	Environmental Management Tool
EPD	Environmental Product Declaration
ES	Expert System
ETL	Extract Transform Load
GA	Grant Agreement
HDD	Hard Disk Drive
HMI	Human-Machine Interface
HTTPS	Hyper Text Transfer Protocol Secured
ICT	Information and communication technology
IoT	Internet of Things
IQS	Intelligent Quarrying System
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KSA	Key Social Area
KTA	Key Technology Area
LAN	Local Area Network
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
ML	Machine Learning
N/A or NA	Not applicable
Nb	Number

Abbreviation	Description
OS	Operating System
RDBMS	Relational Database Management System
REST-API	Representational State Transfer-API
SFTP	Secure File Transfer Protocol
SQL	Structured Query Language
SSD	Solid State Drive
VM	Virtual Machine
WP	Work Package
Unit	Description
€ / \$	Euro / Dollar
Go = Gb	Gibabyte
Ko = Kb	Kilobyte
Mo = Mb	Megabyte
Mn	Minutes
s	Seconds
To = Tb	Terabyte
File Format	Description
.csv (CSV)	Comma-separated values, delimited text file
.json (JSON)	JavaScript Object Notation, Data interchange format
.xml (XML)	Extensible Markup Language

1 Executive Summary

Digital Transformation in Quarrying Operations

The DigiEcoQuarry project represents a significant milestone in the realm of quarrying operations, fostering a digital transformation of traditional practices. The project revolves around the Intelligent Quarrying System (IQS), which serves as the central platform integrating various digital technologies, expert systems, and data sources to streamline operations, enhance efficiency, and provide data-driven insights.

The IQS incorporates a range of components, including a Data Lake platform, Internet of Things (IoT) infrastructure, expert systems, Business Information Modelling (BIM), Artificial Intelligence (AI) services, Data Warehouse, Power BI ecosystem, and Azure cloud services. These components served to build a data collection and storage infrastructure and a data management platform embracing a microservice architecture. Microservices break down the system into modular, manageable components, enhancing agility, scalability, and fault tolerance. This approach streamlines development, maintenance, and updates, allowing for the rapid adaptation of services to evolving quarrying requirements, processes, and operations.

Several quarry processes (Transport, Production, Automation, Environment, etc.) have been implemented within the IQS, and their data models have been defined. Connections using REST APIs have been created, enabling direct communication for data exchange between the expert systems and the IQS according to a newly defined common data format.

In the IQS, Keycloak provides secure authentication and authorization, offering granular control over user permissions based on their roles within the organization (RBAC). Additionally, every interaction within our system occurs over secure HTTPS connections, providing a robust layer of security that safeguards pilot sites data and ensures the privacy of the users.

The data integration process has been implemented at the five pilot sites. Data are flowing at various frequencies (hourly, daily, monthly) depending on the use case. Data integration was achieved using a proxy design pattern adopted by all data providers to push data from expert systems to the IQS and to pull data from the IQS by the data consumers.

In addition to the reporting tools provided by the expert systems, the IQS leveraged the Power BI ecosystem to create comprehensive dashboards and reports that provide insights into KPIs from different facets of quarrying. These tools break down data silos and facilitate data integration from diverse sources, enhancing decision-making capabilities and performance monitoring.

Furthermore, different AI Services are being deployed in the pilot sites, namely a quality and grain size determination service based on cameras, a volume determination service based on videos captured by mobile phones, an anomalies detection service based on audio, a forecast service to improve water and energy consumption, and an advanced, natural language based, document search engine. These services are composed of hardware components, installed in the quarries, along with AI models to process the data generated by the hardware. All outputs are being integrated in the IQS, so they can eventually be visualized in the Power BI dashboards.

Regarding the BIM, the integration of a model-based Common Data Environment (CDE) within the DigiEcoQuarry project has demonstrated an innovative usage of the BIM in quarry environment. By connecting Building Information Modeling (BIM) models with real-time data from various sources, the CDE provides a dynamic digital representation of the quarry. This integration facilitates improved decision-making, better visualization of quarry data, and a proactive approach to maintenance.

In conclusion, in 5 pilot sites, the DigiEcoQuarry project, designed and developed its Intelligent Quarrying System harnessing the power of digital technologies to provide an integrated digitalized automatic process control for aggregates quarries.

2 Introduction

2.1 Concept/Approach

The D4.6 deliverable is the main output of the task 4.5, ICT tools and services integration and deployment, run in the frame of the WP4, “Development of an integrated IoT/BIM/AI platform for smart quarrying [KTA4]”, led by Akkodis, and involving the following other partners: VICAT, CEMEX, HOLCIM, CSI, CIMPOR, UPM-AI, APP and SIGMA.

Within task 4.5, Akkodis is responsible for integrating the developed solution (IoT platform, data lake, application) with the subplatforms, the BIM, and the AI services. Sigma, UPM-AI, and APP are responsible for integrating their developed components into the IQS. Finally, the pilot site provides all necessary support to complete the integration, including data and system integration. All the lines between subsystems in the following figure represent the integration activities we have carried out.

Figure 1. DIGIECOQUARRY's architecture

The deployment activities were initiated in task 4.5 and will continue in task 4.6.

2.2 Deliverable objectives

The objective of the D4.5 deliverable is to provide an overview of the individual elements that make up the IQS platform, the IA Services and the BIM, focusing on their integration and deployment.

After a short introduction, **Section 3 IQS – data management platform** will focus on:

- the IQS components currently deployed, their main functions and availability for each pilot site. An update of IQS components architecture is provided
- the CDMP back-end and the front-end
- the microservices architecture and the interfaces available for data exchange
- the usage of the data lake, the Azure IoT platform, Talend and the databases within the project
- the IQS proxies (connectors) currently implemented and used for the integration
- the Business Management Tools defined and developed. Recently created dashboards and a detailed IQS – Power BI integration view is provided

Section 4 – IQS Data Integration: This section provides a summary of the IQS data integration within the project across all sites and details how the IQS is deployed within the Microsoft Azure infrastructure.

Section 5 – AI Services Data Integration and Deployment: This section provides a final report on the implementation of AI Services in DIGIECOQUARRY.

Section 6 – Data Warehouse Integration and Deployment: This section provides a final report on the Data Warehouse solution implemented.

Section 7 – BIM: This section provides a final report on the model-based Common Data Environment (CDE) and its integration with the data lake.

2.3 Intended audience

The dissemination level of this deliverable is public.

This deliverable is a key input for WP6-Pilot scenarios for quarrying operations monitoring & assessment.

The partners involved in the other work packages such as WP2 (Selection and development of innovative aggregates processing techniques [KTA1, KTA2]), WP3 (Development of sensors, automation, and process control [KTA3]), WP5 (Development of integrated H&S [KTA5] and environmental systems [KTA6]) and WP6 (Pilot scenarios for quarrying operations monitoring [KSA7] & assessment [KSA8]), are also part of the intended audience of this deliverable as they are involved at least as data providers and/or data consumers for the IQS.

Any companies working in the mining industry and wishing to digitalize their business may also be interested in the content of this deliverable.

3 IQS - Data management platform

This section describes the steps performed by AKKODIS for the implementation of the Intelligent Quarry System (IQS) deployed for the five pilot sites. These activities were executed within Work Package 1 Task 1.3, and Work Package 4 Tasks 4.1, 4.2, and 4.5 involving interaction across all work packages.

The first task involved analysing ICT requirements and conducting an inventory of assets. This included:

- defining ICT requirements, performing an inventory of ICT assets,
- conducting a benchmark of the most promising data lake platforms and IoT frameworks,
- defining the architecture and solution to integrate existing platforms,
- identifying data from all quarry processes, expert systems, and external sources.

The second task focused on ICT platform design and implementation. This involved:

- defining all data flows between the expert systems and the IQS,
- designing and implementing the entire IQS, data modelling,
- defining a common data format for all pilot sites to ease data exchange as a first step towards standardization and interoperability,
- implementing all necessary microservices,
- implementing authentication and authorization using Keycloak,
- setting up the data integration platform and implementing an ETL pipeline dedicated to creating KPIs to feed dashboards,
- defining and implementing security measures for IQS including backup policies for all sensitive data and archival strategies for data stored on Azure Data Lake and in databases.

The third task was centered on the IoT platform, which included:

- designing the IoT solution to be developed,
- conducting the first prototyping with IoT Hub, Event Hub, and Event Grid,
- defining and implementing IoT use cases,
- defining the global integration of IoT use cases into the IQS, leading to the creation of a new microservice, Data Lake Browser.

The fourth task involved business management tools, where:

- the global architecture was defined (including identifying dashboard tools such as Power BI),
- the integration strategy for Data Lake, CDMP, Talend, and Power BI was established,
- the microservices, the data model and Talend's pipelines were adapted to generate the data model needed by the Power BI,
- the first prototypes using Power BI were created.

3.1 IQS components achievements

Table 1 describes the IQS components currently deployed, their main functions and availability for each pilot site (HOLCIM, VICAT, CIMPOR, CEMEX, CSI).

Table 1. IQS deployed components

IQS components (Microservices)						Interfaces	Description
	HOLCIM	VICAT	CIMPOR	Cemex	CSI		
Central Data management platform (CDMP)	x	x	x	x	x	Rest API, Web Interface	Main platform dedicated for data collection and data sharing of pilot sites and expert system data (Data upload, Data download, Data ingestion, Data restitution)
Plant production Plant consumption Running Equipment Effectiveness	x	x	x	x		Rest API Web interface	Components dedicated to the data collection and sharing of production data Production: Mass production daily Time: operating and consented time, under load time, lack of feed time, real production, Operating time, efficiency Rate, Performance Rate, Availability, Utilization factor. Consumption: Energy, Fuel, Water (per ton processed) Sales: Production rate, net availability, running equipment effectiveness
Automation (Scada)	x					Rest API	Components dedicated to the data collection and sharing of production data managed by SCADA (automation). Data are flowing from the sensors to the dashboard through the SCADA and the CDMP. Production: t/h, operating, running time, production rate... Consumption: Fuel, Water...
Transport			x	x	x	Rest API Data integration	Components dedicated to the data collection and sharing of Transport (mobile machinery data) produced by Abaut and DH&P systems
Environmental Data Management (EDM)	x	x	x	x	x	Rest API Data integration	Components dedicated to the data collection and sharing of Consumables and Environmental data generated by the PS and by Roctim & Chalmers systems. Consumable per month, EPD Results: Env KPI per Category, module.
IoT data platform and IoT data browser			x			Data lake API	Main IoT platform and IQS IoT component for data collection and data sharing of IoT data (Successful integration with IA: Production Forecast Service, BIM)
Shared data builder tools	x	x	x	x	x	Data upload Metadata	Java application allowing a user to input its credentials, choose files from a local storage, generate metadata, upload and share the data in the data lake (CDMP).
IQS Connectors (proxies)	x	x	x	x		Data upload Metadata Data download	Python program
Integration Deployment in Azure cloud	x	x	x	x	x	5 platforms Secured	Authentication / Authorization (Keycloak) Encrypt communication (Let's Encrypt over Hhttps)

3.2 CDMP

3.2.1 Centralized data management platform

The CDMP developed by AKKODIS is the core of the IQS data exchange system. Its architecture is described in Figure 2: DigiEcoQuarry IQS components architecture. It collects and store data from Pilot Sites and quarry partners and allows IQS users to browse and download data needed for their usage, thanks to the combination of a data lake storing data and several databases storing metadata, raw data and KPIs, enabling cross access to data produced by different processes.

The main CDMP service provides REST APIs for uploading, browsing, accessing, and downloading data. It works in collaboration with other microservices in charge of specific processing according to the data type.

Figure 2: DigiEcoQuarry IQS components architecture

3.2.2 CDMP front-end

The CDMP offers a web interface that facilitates access to uploaded data and data shared among partners at pilot sites, in accordance with the authorizations defined by each site. Each pilot site is equipped with its own CDMP front-end. As illustrated in the following image **Figure 3**: CDMP front-end: Welcome page – “Home” screen, a menu on the main screen grants comprehensive access to the data available in the data lake.

Figure 3: CDMP front-end: Welcome page – “Home” screen

Access to the data catalogue has been made possible thanks to the defined metadata and semantics. This has enabled the provision of an intuitive interface for browsing and searching the available data, as demonstrated in the following two figures: **Figure 4** and **Figure 5**.

Figure 4: CDMP front-end – “Shared Data” screen

1 - Files Available ✕

Actions	Filename	Type	Log Station ID	Format	Comment
	20200812_AT00...	DataSet	0	CSV	String
	20200812_AT00...	DataSet	0	CSV	String
	20200812_AT00...	DataSet	0	CSV	String
	20200812_AT00...	DataSet	0	CSV	String
	metadata_descri...	XSD		XML	Metadata Desc...

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Figure 5: CDMP front-end – “Files available” (Shared data) screen

3.2.3 Microservices & API

For the development of our platform, the IQS embraces a microservices architecture¹ that offers profound benefits. Microservices break down the system into modular, manageable components, enhancing agility, scalability, and fault tolerance. This approach streamlines development, maintenance, and updates, allowing for the rapid adaptation of services to evolving quarrying requirements.

These services run alongside the CDMP main backend application, performing specific treatments according to the type and producer of the uploaded data, and providing access to specific low-level data. All microservices as identified in Figure 6 can be triggered through REST APIs for specific processing, offering a way to connect expert systems to the IQS for data ingestion and retrieval. To automate processes between pilot sites or expert systems and IQS microservices, the design proxy pattern has been adopted and implemented.

¹ Newman, Sam. **Building Microservices: Designing Fine-Grained Systems**. 2nd edition, O'Reilly 2015.

Figure 6: IQS - Microservices and their REST API

A short description of the main microservices is described below. A full description is provided in D4.2.

3.2.3.1 Transport data

Transport services have been designed and implemented to ingest and share transport data automatically sent to the IQS. These data are stored in the pilot site's data lake and in dedicated databases. The transport microservices provide data and KPI ingestion API, and KPI browsing APIs. All data files can be retrieved using CDMP APIs (REST, Web). Two microservices have been developed for Abaut and DH&P systems.

3.2.3.1.1 Abaut transport microservice

The transport service dedicated to Abaut's Expert System manages uploads containing the mobile machineries data (project, region, machines, transport, cycles) of pilot site. Uploads are ingested, parsed, and data are stored in a dedicated database. See D4.2, section 4.1.2.3.5 Interface with Abaut analytics system [KTA 3.2]

3.2.3.1.2 DHP transport microservice

The transport service dedicated to DHP Expert System manages uploads containing asset data (vehicles, plant, oem, asset types, positions, measurements, KPIs, etc.) of CSI pilot site. Uploads are ingested, parsed, and data are stored in a dedicated database. KPIs are calculated by the service and stored in a dedicated database. See D4.2 Section 4.1.2.3.6 Interface with DH&P expert system [KTA 3.3]

3.2.3.1.2.1 Dashboard creation using Power BI

The use of Power BI has been limited to the utilization of aggregated hourly/daily KPI data. As shown in the following figures, the indicators can be viewed by machine, date, and type of indicator:

- The first dashboard as shown in Figure 7 enables the exploration of all indicators for all the trucks.
- The second dashboard in Figure 8 shows a specialized view of fuel usage, idling, and working hours.
- The last two figure (Figure 9, Figure 10) shows the addition of new KPIs related to cost by Power BI. Other dashboards can be easily created based on user needs.

Figure 7: CSI Dashboard - Report 1

Figure 8: CSI Dashboard - Report 2

Figure 9: CSI Dashboard - Report 3

Figure 10: CSI Dashboard - Report 4

3.2.3.1.2.2 Raw Data processing issues

The use of raw data has proven to be complex. Indeed, the processing and storage time of data in a relational database, in our case Postgres, is very long. It takes several hours to process and record all the data in the database of CSI's site (a set of machines). Extracting data from the database is also very time-consuming.

For this reason, we have explored another solution to address this performance constraint. Indeed, the data must be stored and consulted within reasonable times, specifically 15 minutes for storage and less than a minute for consultation.

Furthermore, the use of data must be flexible in the sense that analyses must be possible to allow for data exploration, varied data displays to make correlations between parameters, and finally, to easily create customizable dashboards to exploit time-series data. Lastly, the solution should be inexpensive.

After studying the existing solutions, we opted for the use of the TICK Stack2. Composed of Telegraf, InfluxDB, Chronograf, and Kapacitor, as shown in Figure 11 this open-source solution uses a time-series database which is very suitable for storing and consulting time series data generated by the DHP system. Additionally, InfluxDB integrates with Grafana, a dashboard creation tool that we have studied. The following figure shows the TICK Stack architecture as well as the main features.

Figure 11 : TICK Stack architecture

The following Figure 12 shows the new IQS data flow integrating the TICK Stack and Grafana for managing raw data transport. After receiving the data by the CDMP, the KPIs are stored by the first DHP microservice. This microservice delegates the task of storing the raw data to the DHP Raw Data service. The latter converts the data to the InfluxDB format before storing it. Grafana is connected to the database to create dashboards.

² <https://docs.influxdata.com/>

Figure 12: IQS updated data Flow integrating the Tick Stack

3.2.3.1.2.2.1 Raw data exploration

After integrating IQS with the TICK Stack, data is stored and accessible by asset or parameter filters, as seen via the data exploration interface in the following figures. The storage times for raw data are very good, less than a 5 minutes. Data is directly accessible in the data exploration interface.

An intuitive consultation interface as shown in Figure 13 allows for viewing data over a defined period. Figure 14 shows an example of code to be created with the script editor. These tools are easy to use and can be easily adopted (used) by professionals who do not have much experience with programming:

Figure 13: Data exploration interface

```

from(bucket: "dhp")
  |> range(start: v.timeRangeStart, stop: v.timeRangeStop)
  |> filter(fn: (r) => r["_measurement"] == "AssetRawData")
  |> filter(fn: (r) => r["_field"] == "engineRpm")
  |> filter(fn: (r) => r["asset_id"] == "4db8ab7f-2c4b-465a-ac9e-6da10f1cc403")
  |> aggregateWindow(every: v.windowPeriod, fn: mean, createEmpty: false)
  |> yield(name: "mean")
  
```

Figure 14: InfluxDB Script editor

3.2.3.1.2.2.2 Dashboard creation using Grafana and InfluxDB

Dashboard creation can use either the InfluxDB dashboard or the Grafana3 dashboard. The latter is much more suitable and will be used in the dashboard creation phases.

The following Figure 15 shows an intuitive interface for creating a KPI or parameter visualization interface with Grafana: three parameters pdop, vdop and hdop are selected and displayed in a dashboard.

Figure 15: Grafana dashboard: KPI creation interface

Once validated with users, these interfaces will be used to create global dashboards. As an example, in Figure 16, this dashboard displays a map with truck positions, hourly engine RPM, engine RPM, and fuel usage for the same reporting period (time range).

Figure 16: Grafana dashboard example with Engine RPM, Fuel usage, Truck trucking

3 <https://grafana.com/docs/grafana/latest/getting-started>

3.2.3.2 Plant Production / Automation SCADA

The IQS provides specific REST APIs for uploading plant consumption and production data. The plant production and consumption microservices are supplied with data from the plant’s SCADA system. Automation procedures, including a proxy (connector), have been established to automatically upload production and consumption data directly from the quarry’s Maestro SCADA system to the IQS. This integration is illustrated in the HOLCIM data flow diagram, demonstrating how complete integration of the plant production system with the IQS has been achieved. See D4.2 Section 4.1.2.3.3 Interface with automation & scada system developed by Maestro [KTA 3.1]

Figure 17: Diagram of the plant production data flow within the IQS for HOLCIM pilot site.

For pilot sites without SCADA, the IQS provides other API to upload production data, either manually generated or exported from any other expert system.

After the production data is uploaded, the microservice computes the necessary indicators for monitoring production based on the minimal data defined in the data model.

3.2.3.3 Environmental Data Management

An Environmental Data Management (EDM) system has been designed and implemented within the IQS according to the requirements identified by Chalmers in WP5, as documented in D5.4.

In this solution, sites report plant production data (mass produced in tons) and consumables data (fuel, water, and energy consumption) monthly. Production data are collected either manually or automatically from the plant production SCADA system, while consumables data are semi-automatically collected and uploaded into the system.

An EDM data model has been established to utilize the Environmental Product Declaration (EPD) results obtained following industry standards applicable to the aggregate industry.

Figure 18: Diagram of the environmental data flow within the IQS

All data are stored in the site's data lake, in databases dedicated to plant production and environmental data. These data are made available to relevant data consumers, such as Roctim, for sharing purposes.

Roctim automatically retrieves plant production, consumables, and allocation matrix data via dedicated interface between the IQS and Plantsmith (REST API for data retrieval of environmental data, REST API for downloading of production and consumables data). Once processed within Plantsmith, Roctim can automatically upload the corresponding EPD results using the dedicated interface within the IQS (REST API for uploading LCA/EPD results). These results are stored in the site's data lake and in databases dedicated to EPD results, then made available to relevant data consumers, such as the Environmental Management Tool, for sharing.

EDM’s final REST API list is presented below:

Environmental data management

Environmental data management REST API controllers...

Server: <https://ideq-infag-odmp.francecentral.cloudapp.azure.com:3091/edm> - Generated server url

Filter by tag

- AdvanceConfig** Advance configuration
- AllocationController** Allocation management
- CategoryController** Category management
- ConsumableController** Consumable management
 - GET /api/consumable
 - GET /api/consumable/date/{date}
 - DELETE /api/consumable/date/{date}
 - GET /api/consumable/date/{date}/index/{index}
 - GET /api/consumable/name/{name}/date/{date}
- GroupController** Group management
- Logs** Api for logs retrieving
- PilotJsonController** Api to upload JSON
 - POST /api/pilot/uploadJson
- PlantsmithJson** Api to Consume Plant Smith JSON
 - POST /api/plantsmith/uploadJson/date/{date}
- Result** Api for results displaying
 - GET /api/result/consumPerDu/{date}
 - GET /api/result/fullResult/{date}
 - GET /api/result/largestImpact/{date}
 - GET /api/result/lca/{date}
 - DELETE /api/result/resultData/date/{date}
- ResultAdvance** Api for results displaying
 - GET /api/result/advance/lca/{date}/{category}
 - GET /api/result/advance/lca/{date}/{category}/{moduleName}
 - GET /api/result/advance/lca/{date}/{category}/{moduleName}/{groupName}
 - GET /api/result/advance/lca/allCategory/{date}/{moduleName}/{groupName}
 - GET /api/result/advance/lca/year/{dateStart}/{dateEnd}/{category}/{moduleName}

Figure 19: List of the available endpoints for the EDM (Swagger screen)

The Environmental Management Tool can automatically retrieve these environmental data (via the REST API for downloading EPD results) to produce environmental Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and dashboards. These tools can be used to leverage the EPD results for monitoring, communication, and improvements to the production system from an environmental perspective.

The Environmental Management Tool is a data warehouse environment composed of a Talend process, a PostgreSQL database, a data model, and dashboards designed using Power BI tools accessible through Azure Power Services.

Refer to D4.2 Section 4.1.2.3.9 - Interfaces with applications for environmental impact minimization [KTA 6] and D5.4 Report on Pre-verified EPD documentation for pilot plants based on historical data.

3.2.3.4 Health and Safety Management System

A Health and Safety Management System (HSMS) system has been designed and implemented by AKKODIS within the IQS according to the requirements identified by ITK in WP5, as documented in D5.1.

Within the scope of Work Package 5 (WP5), the focus lies on demonstrating how safety data can be seamlessly integrated into the IQS and establishing integration between the IQS and ITK's Health and Safety system. The diagram below illustrates the data flows between the IQS and ITK H&S system:

Figure 20 Diagram of the health and safety data flow within the IQS

In the developed solution, ITK provides Safety events daily for each monitored system. These events, including the number of warnings and critical events, are transmitted to the IQS H&S Management System through a dedicated interface within the IQS, utilizing REST API for data upload.

The HSMS has been described in D5.1 but the final REST API list and a new dashboard are presented below:

Figure 21: IQS HSMS Rest API Swagger interface

Figure 22 : Example of H&S Events time evolution

3.2.4 Data Lake

Data lakes⁴ have been set up in Microsoft Azure Cloud services to record every data sent to or produced by the IQS.

Azure Data Lake consists of tools for data management, storage in Azure cloud, forming the foundation of the IQS.

The choice of Azure was made following a benchmark conducted in task 4.1. All the details can be found in document D4.1 - "Report on IQS ICT Requirements Analysis and Assets Inventory". IQS data files are stored by microservices within dedicated Azure blob storage containers.

The following figure illustrates the components studied.

⁴ <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/azure/architecture/data-guide/scenarios/data-lake>

Figure 23: Data Lake analysed components

Data are highly secured against lost or corruption using various Azure backup and replication policies. Each pilot site or data provider has its dedicated storage space, accessible only using specific tokens. These tokens are following the authorisation rules defined to containerize data allowing only accredited users to access the data.

In the IQS, the CDMP is the entry point to upload data to or retrieve it from the data lake.

3.2.5 Databases

The IQS incorporates multiple databases tailored to each pilot site. Detailed specifications in task 4.1 have determined that a NoSQL database is not required for this project, and PostgreSQL has been chosen as the preferred hierarchical database solution.

A central database (CDMP) serves as the main database of shared data, housing file’s attributes and metadata descriptions. Acting as the gateway to access data stored in data lakes, it enables browsing, searching, and downloading capabilities for shared data (zip files) or individual data files. Accessible via the CDMP service REST API (communication layer) and its front-end interface (client layer), this database plays a major role in the implementation of the semantic layer of our platform.

Additionally, specific databases have been established for each pilot site, aligning with their respective data management services such as Plant Production and Consumption, Equipment Effectiveness, Environmental Data Management, Transport Data Management and Health and Safety. These databases are populated by corresponding microservices upon parsing raw data. Microservices APIs enable specific browsing of each database, facilitating access to their data by expert systems (e.g.: AI-Services, BIM) or to their KPIs for dashboards creation.

3.2.6 IoT platform

An IoT platform is instantiated on Azure using various IoT components⁵. The development of the IoT platform for the IQS involved designing the IoT solution and configuring the necessary IoT components to build generic applications and IoT scenarios. The following figure illustrates the components studied:

⁵ <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/azure/architecture/reference-architectures/iot>

Figure 24: IoT platform and Open-Source analysed components.

The following figures shows how developed IQS IoT platform is configured to receive, process, store, and share IoT data.

Figure 25: Azure IoT components integration in DEQ

The IoT platform connects the dust sensor in CIMPOR with the data lake and the forecast AI service. IoT data can be used in real-time thanks to the usage of EventHub and EventGrid, or later using the data lake IoT data browser. The former provides access to the data to be used by the forecast AI service developed by Sigma. The data lake browser creates a dynamic catalogue with a front-end, a back-end, and a REST API.

File Name	Size	Date	Type	Access
iotHub-nbzeyczmg3os/02/2024/01/24/06/11.avro	1 KB	24/01/2024	application/octet-stream	sigma-crt
iotHub-nbzeyczmg3os/02/2024/01/24/06/11.json	2 KB	24/01/2024	application/octet-stream	sigma-crt
iotHub-nbzeyczmg3os/01/2024/01/24/06/10.json	2 KB	24/01/2024	application/octet-stream	sigma-crt
iotHub-nbzeyczmg3os/01/2024/01/24/06/10.avro	2 KB	24/01/2024	application/octet-stream	sigma-crt
iotHub-nbzeyczmg3os/00/2024/01/24/06/09.json	2 KB	24/01/2024	application/octet-stream	sigma-crt

Figure 26: Data Lake browser catalogue front-end

3.2.7 Talend

Talend platform has been selected as the main data integration platform⁶. It is used for Extraction, Transformation, and Loading (ETL) of data sets, with a focus on reading PostgreSQL databases and generating content for enriching incoming data.

Talend operates multiple data transformation pipelines specifically designed for managing Transport and Environmental data. These ETL pipelines are linked to Transport and EDM microservices to produce the necessary KPIs for subsequent processes (utilizing Power BI). Talend creates all dimensions and facts of the datasets needed by Power BI for the dynamic computation of KPI.

In DEQ, Talend enables all inter-system data integration scenarios. Thanks to its multiple connectors, it allows for simple interconnection of systems, thus solving the problem of silos. Moreover, all interfaces that have not yet been connected, e.g., SAP, will be able to do so once the security restrictions are lifted.

Finally, the management of Talend processes has been fully integrated into the IQS to simplify process initiation and monitoring directly from the CDMP.

3.3 Data proxies

Python programs provided to partners, the proxies are tools aiming to simplify data management and integration.

There are two categories of proxy:

- Data ingestion proxies:

This category of proxies is used to upload data from PS or quarry partners to CDMP. They can read data from a specific folder or be active and request data from partners' expert systems. Data is tagged, described, packaged and upload to the dedicated service of CDMP.

- Data access proxies:

This category of proxies is used to ease data access and download, using metadata filtering.

The proxies can be launched automatically, from CDMP platform or from partners systems, making data ingestion to CDMP automatic. Therefore, they are key tools to integrate partners expert systems and IQS together allowing and easing automatic and on demand data flows.

⁶ <https://www.talend.com/resources/get-started-talend-open-studio-data-integration/>

Table 2. DIGIECOQUARRY's Script

Partners	Name	Description
All	deq-proxy-multiple-files	Script to upload any files
	deq-proxy-file-download	Script to download any files
	deq-proxy-zip-download	Script to download a shared data archive
Pilot Sites	deq-proxy-upload-consumable	Script to upload consumables data files
	deq-proxy-production-consumption-ree	Script to upload plant production data (xls file)
Metso	deq-proxy-metso	Script to upload Metso data files
Mintek	deq-proxy-mintek	Script to upload Mintek data files
Abaut	deq-proxy-abaut	Script to upload Abaut data files
Arco	deq-proxy-arco	Script to upload Arco data files
DHP	deq-proxy-dhp-asset-values	Script to upload DHP raw data files
	deq-proxy-dhp	Script to upload any other DHP data files
ITK	deq-proxy-itk	Script to upload ITK health and safety data files
Maestro	deq-proxy-maestro-production	Script to upload Maestro production data
	deq-proxy-maestro-param	Script to upload Maestro param data files
	deq-proxy-maestro	Script to upload other Maestro data files / Integrated in Scada tools
Metso	deq-proxy-metso	Script to upload Metso data files
Mintek	deq-proxy-mintek	Script to upload Mintek data files
Roctim	deq-proxy-upload-lca-results	Script to upload LCA result data files / Integrated in Scada tools
	deq-proxy-roctim	Script to upload any other Roctim data files
Sandvik	deq-proxy-sandvik	Script to upload Drilling reports data files
UPM	deq-proxy-upm-m	Script to download any Drilling data and enable data integration with UPM MATLAB environment
Sigma	deq-proxy-sigma	Script to upload Sigma data files

3.4 Business management tools

The primary objective of our Reporting and Management tools is to provide visualization and reporting capabilities for various categories of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). These KPIs can originate from expert systems, can be calculated and aggregated by the Data Warehouse after data transfer to the data lake or generated at a later stage using Power BI. Leveraging the Power BI ecosystem facilitates data integration from multiple sources, including databases, remote file storage, data warehouse, REST API, etc. This capability allows us to create indicators that span different expert systems and company business units, effectively breaking down data silos.

The following WBS diagram shows the variety of dashboards that can be created thanks to the digitalization implemented in the DEQ project.

Figure 27. Variety of dashboards that can be created

For the creation of dashboards with Power BI, the data is organized into multiple databases as shown in the next figure, each grouping its indicators that will be used to create a specific dataset. This dataset will be used to build a report (Business Management Tools) containing several dashboards. To enable the creation of a decision support tool applicable to all processes, we have created applications called Apps. These Apps consolidate multiple dashboards that can be refreshed at varying frequencies to minimize environmental impacts.

Figure 28. Apps structure

3.4.1 Power BI Dashboards deployment

In the context of a specific site, all the dashboards created can be shared directly or included in a Power BI Application⁷. The chosen solution will be defined individually for the the pilot site. However, the organization of the dashboards is constrained by the rules and the development process recommended by Power BI. Hence a dashboard must be defined in a dedicated workspace accessible to dashboard's editors and should be dedicated to a specific topic or function

⁷ <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/power-bi/>

(Environmental data, production, transport) then, the aggregation of multiple dashboards can be performed in a Power BI application accessible to specific pilot sites' users.

The following Figure 29 shows the Power BI Pipeline environments for HOLCIM as an example. The other pipelines created for CEMEX, CIMPOR, CSI and VICAT follow the same process. The datasets and reports are managed in three workspaces dedicated to Development, Test, and Production. This mode of operation defines a mature development process that adopts software development best practices.

Figure 29: Power BI Pipeline environment for HOLCIM

3.4.2 Power-BI Dashboard

As part of the project, AKKODIS developed dashboards and applications for the five sites that consolidates all the dashboards. The dashboards utilize the collected data. Due to a lack of data for multiple reasons described in Section: 4 IQS data integration, some dashboards contain test data.

The following figure shows an example of an application that includes multiples dashboards. Each one contains its visualizations.

Figure 30. Example of Business Management Tools App with multiple reports for one site

⁸ <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/fabric/cicd/deployment-pipelines/intro-to-deployment-pipelines>

Figure 31. Dashboard showing plant production data and various KPI.

Figure 32. Zoom on an environmental dashboard showing EPD report data.

Figure 33. Example of Business Management Tools App with multiple reports for two sites

Figure 34. Dashboards comparing time distribution and various target rates of two sites. Site 2 data are dummy.

Figure 35. Zoom on a dashboard showing a dashboard with Health & Safety data (with test data).

3.4.3 Power-BI Environment

The following Figure 36 shows the final components view of the system. Thus, Power BI dashboards use multiple data sources: either SQL databases or data stored in the data lake. Talend processes are run to update the data model necessary for generating Power BI reports. Access to Power BI reports is restricted to a list of users defined in Active Directory. All report update operations are done through the Power BI Desktop interface.

Figure 36: Power-BI Ecosystem integration with the IQS

4 IQS data integration

This section provides a summary of the IQS data integration within the project across all sites. The figure below illustrates the interfaces available at the IQS via its central data management platform (CDMP). These interfaces facilitate interaction for any data provider or consumer with the IQS. The utilization of these interfaces varies depending on the integration scenario with each expert system or KTA at each site.

Figure 37. interfaces available at the IQS via its central data management platform (CDMP).

The subsequent tables outline all existing data integration scenarios and the current status of data availability in the data lake at this stage.

This status can be Yes or No. Unsuccessful data integration status is attributed to one or several of the following:

- a: automation not attained yet,
- b: data partially available,
- c: manual data integration is time-consuming,
- d: scenarios not yet implemented,
- e: inability to connect with the expert system,
- f: data shared offline,
- g: data unavailability at the current time and impacted downstream process,
- h: data not defined,
- i: data accessible directly through expert system.

4.1.1 HOLCIM data integration results:

Table 3. HOLCIM data integration summary

Data provider	Upload solution	Expert system - API	Download solution	KTA	Data consumer	Data availability status in the data lake
HOLCIM	Manual	N/A	Manual	KTA2.2	Mintek	Yes
	Manual	N/A	N/A	KTA6	MUL	No ^f
	Manual	N/A	Automatic	KTA4.4	AKKODIS (EMT) Dashboards	Yes
	Manual	N/A	Automatic	KTA6	Chalmers/Roctim	Yes

Mintek	Manual	N/A	Manual	KTA2.2	HOLCIM	No ^f
Arco	Automatic	Arco API	Automatic Arco	KTA3.1	Maestro	Yes
Maestro	Automatic	Maestro API	Automatic CDMP API	KTA3.1	HOLCIM	Yes
		Maestro API	Automatic CDMP API	KTA4.1	APP	Yes
		Maestro API	Automatic CDMP API	KTA4.4	AKKODIS (BMT)	Yes ^{b,c,e}
		Maestro API	Automatic CDMP API	KTA6	Chalmers/Roctim	Yes ^{b,c}
Abaut	Manual	N/A	Abaut ES	KTA3.2	HOLCIM	No ^f
APP	Manual	N/A	Manual	KTA4.1	HOLCIM	Yes
Sigma/UPM-AI (AI-Services)	Automatic	Sigma API (CDMP Proxy)	Automatic	KTA4.4	Sigma/UPM-AI (DWH/BMT)	No ^{f,a}
Sigma/UPM-AI (DWH/BMT)	Automatic	DWH API	Automatic	KTA4.2	Sigma(BMT)	No ^a
Chalmers	Automatic	Plantsmith API	Automatic CDMP API	KTA4.4	AKKODIS (EMT)	Yes
	Manual	N/A	Manual	KTA6	HOLCIM	Yes

4.1.2 CSI data integration results:

Table 4.. CSI data integration summary

Data Provider	Upload solution	Expert system - API	Download solution	KTA	Data consumer	Data availability status in the data lake
CSI	Manual	N/A	Automatic	KTA4.4	AKKODIS (EMT) Dashboards	Yes
	Manual	N/A	N/A	KTA6	MUL	No ^f
	Manual	N/A	Automatic	KTA6	Chalmers/Roctim	Yes ^b
DH&P	Automatic	DH&P API	Manual	KTA3.3	CSI	Yes
			Automatic CDMP API	KTA4.1	APP	Yes

			Automatic CDMP API	KTA4.4	AKKODIS Mobile Machinery Service	Yes
			Manual	KTA6	MUL	Yes
			Manual	KTA6	Chalmers/Roctim	Yes ^b
APP	Manual	N/A	Manual	KTA4.1	CSI	Yes
Sigma/UPM-AI (AI-Services)	Automatic	SIGMA API (CDMP Proxy)	Automatic	KTA4.4	Sigma/UPM-AI (DWH/BMT)	No ^{f,g}
Sigma/UPM-AI (DWH/BMT)	Automatic	DWH API	Automatic	KTA4.2	Sigma(BMT)	No ^{f,a}
Chalmers Roctim	Automatic	Plantsmith API	Automatic CDMP API	KTA4.4	AKKODIS (EMT)	Yes
	Manual	N/A	Manual	KTA6	CSI	Yes
ITK	Automatic	ITK H&S API	Automatic	KTA 5	AKKODIS (H&S MT) Dashboards	Yes ^g

4.1.3 VICAT data integration results:

Table 5. VICAT data integration summary

Data Provider	Upload solution	Expert system - API	Download solution	KTA	Data consumer	Data availability status in the data lake
VICAT - Eutotek Scada	Automatic	Euroteck API	Automatic	KTA3.1	Arco	No ^{a,e,g}
VICAT	Manual	N/A	N/A	KTA6	MUL	No ^f
	Manual	N/A	Automatic	KTA4.4	AKKODIS (EMT) Dashboards	Yes
	Manual	N/A	Automatic	KTA6	Chalmers/Roctim	Yes
ITK	Automatic	ITK H&S API	Automatic	KTA 5	AKKODIS (H&S MT) Dashboards	Yes ^g
Metso	Manual	Metso API	Manual	KTA2.1	VICAT	Yes ^g

APP	Manual	N/A BIM	TBD	KTA4.1	VICAT	Yes
Sigma/UPM-AI (AI-Services)	Automatic	SIGMA API (CDMP Proxy)	Automatic	KTA4.4	Sigma/UPM-AI (DWH/BMT)	No ^{a,f}
Sigma/UPM-AI (DWH-BMT)	Automatic	DWH API	Automatic	KTA4.2	SIGMA(BMT)	No ^a
Chalmers/Roctim	Automatic	Plantsmith	Automatic	KTA4.4	AKKODIS (EMT)	Yes
	Manual	N/A	Manual	KTA6	VICAT	Yes
Maestro (Scada)	Automatic	In progress	Automatic	KTA3.1	VICAT	No ^g
		Maestro API	Automatic CDMP API	KTA4.5	AKKODIS (BMT)	No ^{g,c,e}
ITK	Automatic	ITK H&S API	Automatic	KTA 5	AKKODIS (H&S MT) Dashboards	Yes ^g

4.1.4 CIMPOR data integration results:

Table 6. CIMPOR data integration summary

Data Provider	Upload solution	Expert system - API	Download solution	KTA	Data consumer	Data availability status in the data lake
CIMPOR	Manual	N/A	Automatic CDMP API	KTA4.2	Sigma/UPM-AI (AI-Services)	No ^f
	Manual	N/A	Automatic CDMP API	KTA4.4	Sigma/UPM-AI (DWH/BMT)	No ^{c,e}
	Manual	N/A	Automatic CDMP API	KTA4.4	AKKODIS (EMT) Dashboards	Yes ^b
	Manual	N/A	N/A	KTA6	MUL	No ^f
	Manual	N/A	Manual	KTA6	Chalmers/Roctim	Yes ^b
Arco	Automatic	Arco API	CDMP API	KTA3.1	CIMPOR	No ^a
		Arco API	CDMP API	KTA4.4	Sigma/UPM-AI (AI-Services)	No ^{a,c,e}
		Arco API	Automatic CDMP API	KTA4.4	AKKODIS (BMT)	No ^{a,c,e}
		Arco API	CDMP API	KTA6	Chalmers/Roctim	No ^{a,c,e}
Abaut	Automatic/Manual	Abaut ES	Manual	KTA3.2	CIMPOR	Yes ^{f,g}
		Abaut ES	Automatic	KTA4.2	Sigma/UPM-AI (AI-Services)	Yes ^{b,g}

		About ES	Automatic CDMP API	KTA4.4	Sigma/UPM-AI (DWH/BMT)	N/A
		About ES	Automatic CDMP API	KTA4.4	AKKODIS (BMT)	Yes ^{b,g}
		About ES	N/A	KTA6	Chalmers/Roctim	No ^g
APP	Manual	N/A	Manual	KTA4.1	CIMPOR	Ok
Sigma/UPM-AI (AI-Services)	Automatic	N/A	Automatic CDMP API	KTA4.2	CIMPOR	Yes
	Automatic	N/A	Automatic CDMP API	KTA4.4	Sigma/UPM-AI (DWH/BMT)	Yes
Sigma/UPM-AI (DWH/BMT)	Automatic	DWH API	Automatic	KTA4.2	Sigma/UPM-AI (AI-Services)	No ^a
	Automatic	DWH API	Automatic	KTA4.2	Sigma(BMT)	No ^a
Chalmers/ Roctim	Automatic	Plantsmith API	Automatic	KTA4.4	AKKODIS (EMT)	Yes
	Manual	N/A	Manual	KTA6	CIMPOR	Yes
ITK	Automatic	ITK H&S API	Automatic	KTA 5	AKKODIS (H&S MT) Dashboards	Yes ^g

4.1.5 Cemex data integration results:

Table 7. CEMEX data integration summary

Data Provider	Upload solution	Expert system - API	Download solution	KTA	Data consumer	Data availability status in the data lake
CEMEX	Manual	N/A	Manual	KTA1.x	UPM-M	No ^f
	Manual	N/A	Manual	KTA1.x	Sandvik	No ^f
	Manual	N/A	Manual	KTA1.x	Maxam	No ^f
	Manual	N/A	Manual	KTA1.x KTA3.2	About	No ^f
	Manual	N/A	Manual	KTA4.2	Sigma/UPM-AI (AI-Services)	No ^f
	Manual	N/A	Automatic	KTA4.4	AKKODIS (EMT) Dashboards	Yes ^b
	Manual	N/A	N/A	KTA6	MUL	No ^f
	Manual	N/A	TBD	KTA6	Chalmers/Roctim	Yes
UPM-M	Manual	N/A	Manual	KTA1.x	CEMEX	No ^f
	Manual	N/A	Manual	KTA1.x	Sandvik	No ^f
	Manual	N/A	Manual	KTA1.x	Maxam	No ^f
Sandvik	Automatic	Sandvik API	Manual / CDMP API	KTA1.x	UPM-M	Yes
	Manual	N/A	Manual	KTA1.x	CEMEX	No ^f
	Manual	N/A	Manual	KTA1.x	Maxam	No ^f
Maxam	Manual	N/A	Manual	KTA1.x	UPM-M	No ^f
	Manual	N/A	Manual	KTA1.x	Sandvik	No ^f
	Manual	N/A	Manual	KTA1.x	CEMEX	No ^f
About	Manual	About ES	Manual	KTA1.x	UPM-M	No ^f
		About ES	Manual	KTA6	MUL	No ^f
		About ES	Manual	KTA1.x KTA3.2	CEMEX	No ^f

		About ES	Automatic CDMP API	KTA4.2	Sigma/UPM-AI (AI-Services)	No ^f
		About ES	Automatic CDMP API	KTA4.4	AKKODIS (BMT)	Yes ^{b,g}
		About ES	Manual	KTA6	Chalmers/Rocticm	No ^g
App	Manual	N/A	Manual	KTA4.1	CEMEX	Yes
Sigma/UPM-AI (AI-Services)	Automatic	SIGMA API (CDMP Proxy)	Automatic	KTA4.4	Sigma/UPM-AI (DWH/BMT)	No ^a
Sigma/UPM-AI (DWH/BMT)	Automatic	DWH API	Automatic	KTA4.2	Sigma (BMT)	No
Chalmers/Rocticm	Automatic	Plantsmith API	Automatic	KTA4.4	AKKODIS (EMT)	Yes
	Manual	N/A	Manual	KTA6	CEMEX	Yes

4.1.6 Deployment

In this section, a detailed deployment diagram of the Intelligent Quarrying System (IQS) is presented. This diagram provides a comprehensive overview of the system's architecture, outlining how various components and services are distributed across different layers and environments. Understanding the deployment structure is essential to grasp the system's scalability, reliability, and interactions among its components.

Figure 38: Diagram for the DEQ IQS deployment.

This diagram represents the deployment for one pilot site.

In our architecture, Azure VMs are configured with standard sizes to meet the requirements of various components within the system. Specifically:

CDMP and Database Nodes: We utilize Azure B4ms VMs, which are equipped with 4 virtual CPUs (vCPU) and 16 GB of RAM. These VMs are chosen for their robust computing power and memory capacity, making them well-suited for the tasks associated with our CDMP and Database nodes.

Keycloak and Talend Nodes: For Keycloak and Talend nodes, we opt for Azure B2ms VMs. These VMs feature 2 vCPUs and 8 GB of RAM, providing a balanced and efficient configuration to handle the responsibilities of these components.

In our system, all services and communication channels are meticulously secured. To ensure data integrity and confidentiality, we employ Let's Encrypt certificates to authenticate all services and encrypt communication. This means that every interaction within our system takes place over secure HTTPS connections, providing a robust layer of security that safeguards pilot sites data and ensures the privacy of the users.

4.1.6.1 Risk related to the IQS deployment in Azure

IQS breakdown caused by a cyberattack on Microsoft Azure has been identified as an important risk. The consequences could be: disruptions to service delivery, compromised data integrity, financial losses or damage to reputation. To address this risk the following measure were identified and are applied:

AKKODIS utilizes the standard ISO 27002 for customer projects, including:

- Implementation of industry-standard security protocols and best practices, such as encryption, access control, and intrusion detection systems
- Usage of the Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVE) dictionary to identify publicly known cybersecurity vulnerabilities
- Utilization of various tools like Rapid7, Tanium, and Sentinel One, Endpoint Detection and Response (EDR)
- Continuous monitoring and assessment of all Azure's security vulnerabilities, prompt application of patches, and updates to address known vulnerabilities.
- Collaboration with Azure's security team and leveraging their expertise to enhance our security posture and response capabilities.
- Ongoing employee training and awareness programs to promote cybersecurity hygiene and incident response readiness.

IQS utilizes Keycloak⁹ for identity and access management and Let's Encrypt to encrypt communication.

IQS implements backup policies for all sensitive data (database, data lake).

An archival strategy is applied to both the data stored on Azure Data Lake and in the databases.

⁹ <https://www.keycloak.org/>

5 AI Services data integration and deployment

5.1 Introduction

The services design implementation of the AI services in DEQ was described in D4.3. The same applies to the Data warehouse design implementation, this time in D4.4.

As Figure 39 illustrates, the integration of the AI services can be seen as a flow of different and very well determined services as explained below.

- **Hardware installation on site:**

For the quality determination and grainsize determination services a similar architecture and component elements were used and will be described later on in this chapter.

For the stockpile volume calculation service, no specific HW was needed to be installed at the quarry, only a phone application is required to capture videos and images that are used for the calculation. Moreover, drone flights and satellite images were used to check the validity of the results obtained on the volume calculations.

For the production and consumption forecast service, in order to obtain detailed and automatically important data (in terms also of data points: several values are obtained daily), the use and design of different sensors was introduced: dust sensors, meteorological station, water consumption pulse counters. The latter required rather complex installation procedures that will be detailed here under.

For the anomalies detection service, again it needed the design of a specific sensor needed to record sounds and vibrations. The latter also needs for a simple installation procedure again detailed below.

For the Metaquarry process, we are talking about a service running typically in the cloud on specific servers. The quarry operators only need to connect via a web browser. It is important to highlight that it relies on the fact that documentation of the quarries has to be weather uploaded on file Sharepoint or the service allows for the connection of specific companies Microsoft Sharepoint service or Google cloud servers in order to implement the documentation management.

- **Communication networks provisioning:**

For the services needing specific hardware to be installed, they also needed the deployment of a specific network able to connect to the cloud (internet) using a modem and in some cases 2 different network stages: a local network connecting the sensors and a gateway to the internet using a cellular networks (4G or 3G). For the latter, IoT SIMS are being used together with their corresponding cellular modem in the gateways/PCs. More details can be found in the following sections.

- **Cloud AI data and device management platforms:**

The data sent from the different servers and gateways in the quarries are firstly stored at specific device and data platforms which have the possibility to manage each device independently and control the data flow.

- **AI service algorithms implementation servers deployment:**

The data stored at the above platforms is then processed on servers implemented in the cloud and the results are used to generate the designed Dashboards.

- **IQS data transmission and processing for the AI services:**

The results of the different analysis and calculus are then inserted in the Datalake using the available CDMP APIs. These data are then filtered and rearranged on the Data Warehouse using the specifically designed data pipelines.

Finally, the data in the Data Warehouse can be queried using SQL programming to get the KPIs already processed before inserting the data into Power Bi to display the graphical KPI interface related to the developed services.

Figure 39. DEQ AI services deployment processes

The Data Warehouse integration and deployment the flow was much simpler since we are talking of a service deployed over a commercial Google platform: BigQuery. Moreover, the Data Warehouse is part of the IQS platform. Most of the activities were referred to configuration and programming in order to obtain a personalized instance of BigQuery tuned to the needs of DEQ and being able to receive data from various sources (even external web resources) and transmit data to Power BI. The schema below (Figure 40) represents the deployment and integration processes followed for the Data Warehouse in order to implement the personalized DEQ instance.

For the interfaces and Data analysis it is important to mention that specific routines can be written in several programming languages such as Javascript or Python for example. The use of queries directly in the Data Warehouse has been chosen as the main strategy to avoid and diminish the load to Power BI. It is much faster to implement data analysis directly in the same infrastructure as of the one used for the tables.

Figure 40. Integration and deployment processes for the Data Warehouse

5.2 Quality determination service integration and deployment at CEMEX

5.2.1 Service integration and deployment

In D4.3 this part of the deployment was already covered and for the sake of clarity, some of the relevant content is copied below. This section includes some updates to resolve the latest issues encountered at the time of writing that deliverable.

The quality determination service (hardware) is being installed in the primary section of the treatment plant at the Valdilecha-CEMEX plant. The location is pinpointed in the following picture from the quarry. The main goal is to provide the amount of clay that is entering in the treatment plant but it is not possible to install a computer vision system in the exploitation front or inside the dump truck access platform in the primary. Therefore, this service is focused on Computer Vision system installed in different parts of the primary (crusher and C3 conveyor belt) whose combination gives us the total and mixed material that entered in the plant.

Figure 41: Location of the primary section in the Valdilecha-CEMEX Pilot.

The hardware components of the quality determination service are two cameras with lenses, an industrial PC (with modem + external antenna, PCI board to interface and power the cameras, SIM card), a screen and two LED arrays which will be used to have a controlled lighting environment at C3 conveyor area. For the camera and optical lens selection several aspects have been evaluated: working distance; field of view; fragment size to detect and pixel resolution; color or monochrome type image sensor; image transfer speed, etc. Now, in the figure below a schema of the primary section in the Valdilecha Pilot is shown. Here the two camera installation spots can be found, marked with positions 1, above the crusher, and 2 over the conveyor belt C3. On the latter, all material that has been discarded by the primary screen/rollers is fed.

Figure 42: Schema of the Valdilecha-CEMEX's primary and camera settings.

Sigma subcontracted the mechanical fitting of the different elements to the official electrical installer of the quarry. This specialized equipment is required for collection data and once the CV model is deployed, the hardware will be used for analysis of data exclusively for this project. In October 2023 the installation was carried out at the Valdilecha-CEMEX site, with the exception of one camera for which a special attachment was needed. The most important challenge that was

faced here is the placement of the camera over the primary crusher: it has to be attached to the control booth of the crusher but in a place where the camera cannot be hit by the hydraulic hammer sometimes used for big rocks not being crushed. Due to the latter issue, the camera was not fixed at the time of writing D4.3 and an articulated fixing arm had to be ordered to be able to adjust the line of sight of the camera. A second camera and lights were installed in the C3 conveyor belt as explained above, and the related pictures are appended below. In these photographs, the camera installed is shown and part of the equipment installed in the primary booth: the controlling PC and a screen that can be used to watch the two camera outputs. At some hours of the day the sun hits the conveyor belt, so the quarry had to do some adjustment to have a controlled light environment.

Figure 43: C3 Camera equipment (camera, lens and two LED arrays)

Figure 44: Primary crusher booth equipment (screen, industrial PC and external antenna)

After submitting D4.3, these last issues were resolved, so the status of this service integration and implementation is as follows (the related pictures are appended below):

- An articulated fixing arm was added to the crusher camera.
- The crusher camera is installed.
- The C3 conveyor belt camera is adjusted, and the aluminium profile was cut to prevent it from protruding.
- The sailcloth over the C3 conveyor belt is expanded to prevent the entry of dirt and control the light.

Figure 45: Final installation of quality determination service equipment (at crusher, C3 conveyor belt and primary booth).

To validate the hardware at the quarry and installation, several on-site tests have been done to adjust the camera location and settings (exposure time, frame rate, gain, gamma, white balance, region of interest, etc.) using its camera viewer.

Figure 46: Camera viewer with an image received from the crusher camera (left) and C3 camera (right).

Figure 47: Captured images by the crusher camera (left) and C3 conveyor belt camera (right) at the Valdilecha-CEMEX's primary.

Communications and service monitoring modules have been developed to enable remote access using OpenVPN network, communicate the computer vision system with other elements, and sending data using 3G or 4G via the IoT network and platform of Telefonica. Furthermore, a service monitoring has been implemented and notifications are sent in case service status change is detected (agent is not available, restarted, etc.). Therefore, when the PC is turned on, communication and acquisition start, and a basic interface is launched with the two images captured by the cameras. The PC with the attached 4G modem is programmed to automatically reboot itself if necessary. The system interface does not require user interaction and has been implemented this way to show the operator that the system is working without any action from his/her side.

The image acquisition software has been developed using the SDK provided by the camera vendor to listing currently connected cameras, controlling camera features, acquiring images from the camera and notifications about camera connections or disconnections. This module has been developed taking into account the following considerations: camera features, calibration, error control and synchronize process to create a dataset to train a model. For this last consideration, currently the images are sending to the Sigma servers because to build a robust and accurate computer vision model is needed data collection, preparation, annotation, model training and evaluation. Once the Computer Vision models are deployed at the quarry, this data will not be sent unless a refined dataset is required.

5.2.2 Data integration in the IQS

The aim of this service is to estimate the quality of aggregates during production and, also to detect possible warning alarms (for example, about the size of the material). The aggregate quality determination of the material in the Valdilecha-CEMEX quarry should provide the amount of clay / limestone that is entering in the treatment plant meaning if there are a high quantity of clay that there is an issue at the extraction and material selection processes. To obtain it, a segmentation and colorimetry algorithm is applied to the pre-processed images to classify and identify each fragment individually. Subsequently, relevant information for the warning alarm and quality determination is extracted in a json file daily (amount of clay / limestone, colour of each category based on RGB/Munsell colour system, the size of the fragments in the case of the crusher, ...). Finally, the quality results from the crusher plus C3 conveyor belt are combined in a json file as the output of the Quality service. This json file is sent from the quarry using 3-4G networking (a modem and a SIM are integrated on the local PC) throughput provided by the Movistar Spanish IOT network. Samples of the proposed data integration scheme in the IQS and a daily json file from the C3 conveyor belt computer vision system are shown below.

Figure 48: Scheme about the Quality determination service results integration in the IQS.

```

{
  "Timestamp": "2024-05-28T09:26:12.301572",
  "Background%": 51.205353149042764,
  "Material%": 48.794646850957236,
  "Clay%": 30.485279399266417,
  "Limestone%": 18.30936745169082,
  "TotalPX": 2861568,
  "ClayPX": 87235700,
  "LimestonePX": 52393500,
  "ClayMeanRGB": "#493d29",
  "LimestoneMeanRGB": "#544832",
  "ClayMedianRGB": "#4a3d29",
  "LimestoneMedianRGB": "#544731",
  "ClayModeRGB": "#493e29",
  "LimestoneModeRGB": "#554331",
  "ClayCustomRGB": "#1a3e2a",
  "LimestoneCustomRGB": "#554933",
  "ClayMunsell": "2.8Y 2.6/2.2",
  "LimestoneMunsell": "3.2Y 3.1/2.3",
  "ClayRoundedMunsell": "2.5Y 3/2",
  "LimestoneRoundedMunsell": "2.5Y 3/2",
  "ClaylinearRGB": "#110c06",
  "LimestonelinearRGB": "#171108"
},

```

Figure 49: A sample daily json file from the C3 conveyor belt computer vision system.

The output of the Quality service is then uploaded to the IQS using the CDMP proxy, a tool, developed by AKKODIS, that allows to upload data to the Data Lake. This tool expects a zip file that contains the output data itself, along with a metadata file that describes the output. In this case, a sample metadata file is shown below:

```
<PS_Shared_Data xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance"
xsi:noNamespaceSchemaLocation="DEQ-CDMP-Shared-Data-Interface-V0.3.xsd">
  <Pilot_Site>CEMEX</Pilot_Site>
  <Quarry_Process>AI Services (KTA4.2)</Quarry_Process>
  <Sub_Process>Quality service</Sub_Process>
  <Sharing_Description>Output for the Quality service</Sharing_Description>
  <Sharing_Date>2024-05-26</Sharing_Date>
  <Shared_Item>
    <Shared_File_Identifier>11110</Shared_File_Identifier>
    <Item_Sharing_Comment>Comment</Item_Sharing_Comment>
    <Shared_Data_DQCT_Report>
      <File_Name>String</File_Name>
      <DQCT_Status>QC_PASSED_WITH_WARNING</DQCT_Status>
    </Shared_Data_DQCT_Report>
    <Shared_Data_Files>
      <Shared_File>
        <File_Name>cemex_quality_20240526.json</File_Name>
        <Type>DataSet</Type>
        <Format>JSON</Format>
        <Log_StationId>0</Log_StationId>
        <Comment>String</Comment>
      </Shared_File>
    </Shared_Data_Files>
  </Shared_Item>
</PS_Shared_Data>
```

Figure 50: A sample metadata file of the quality service output.

Whenever a new output is produced by the service, a script is called to generate the metadata file and zip it together with the output. Once the zip file is ready, the script makes a POST request to the CDMP containing the zip file:

```
requests.post(cmdp_url, files={"archive": file_name}, headers={'Authorization': 'Bearer ' + token})
```

This request needs to be authenticated. A token can be obtained by sending a POST request with valid credentials to the CDMP, which will return the mentioned token:

```
requests.post(url, data={'client_id': 'python-cli', 'username': 'sigma', 'password': 'XXXX', 'grant_type': 'password'})
```

Once the data is in the Data Lake, a *pipeline* is set up to extract this data, aggregate and add it to the Data Warehouse, structured according to the table presented in section 6.4. An in-depth description of this process can be found in section 3 of deliverable D4.4.

5.2.3 Service outputs

The quality determination service will provide the quality of aggregates that are entering in the treatment of Valdilecha-CEMEX and also detect possible warning alarms. The images below show a preliminary version of the PowerBI dashboards. The alarm dashboard is shared with the grain size determination service.

Figure 51. Main dashboard for Valdilecha-CEMEX quarry.

Figure 52. Quality determination dashboard with selected date (left). In case the colour and weather information are of value for the quarry, the right graphical is considered for addition to quality determination board.

Figure 53. Alarm dashboard for Valdilecha-CEMEX quarry.

5.3 Grain size determination service integration and deployment at CEMEX

5.3.1 Service integration and deployment

Here again the relevant content that was already written in D4.3 is here below copied. This section includes some updates to resolve the latest issues encountered at the time of writing that deliverable.

The rain size determination (granulometry) service will provide the size of the particles in aggregates to automate the process of determining whether the material meets technical specifications. The granulometry service (hardware) is installed in the secondary section of the treatment plant at the Valdilecha-CEMEX plant. The location is pinpointed in the following picture from the quarry. Here you can find the different silos with the produced material sizes stocks.

Figure 54: Location of the secondary section in the Valdilecha-CEMEX Pilot.

The computer vision system is based on one camera with lenses, an industrial PC (with modem + external antenna, PCI board to interface and power the camera, SIM card) and two LED arrays which will be used to have a controlled lighting environment at the conveyor area. Now, to be more precise, a schema of the secondary section is displayed below, highlighting (orange square) the position where the camera is installed, above the conveyor belt C33 from the 4/20mm silo that serves the correspondent stockpile.

Figure 55: CEMEX-Valdilecha Secondary map and. Área where the CV camera is installed

In October 2023 the installation was carried out at the Valdilecha-CEMEX site. Sigma subcontracted the mechanical fitting of the different elements to the official electrical installer of the quarry. The most important challenge encountered was the need to place the controlling PC of the camera and power supply at a relatively long distance from the camera itself: more than 20 m away. In the figure below the camera and lights installation placement and the equipment booth are signaled with yellow circles.

Figure 56: View of the installation points in Valdilecha's secondary.

Now pictures of the installed camera and booth equipment in October 2023 are shown below. The antenna positioning, at that moment, permits only a 15-20% of 4G coverage. This can be improved by attaching a longer cable to look for an optimal antenna position reaching a better 4G coverage. As in the quality service, at some hours of the day the sun hits the conveyor belt, so some adjustments are needed by the quarry to have a controlled light environment. Although lighting is controlled in some hours, the illumination of the captured images varies slightly depending on the amount of material present in the conveyor belt, so once the light is controlled, some adjustment to the camera is needed.

Figure 57: Pictures of the camera, antenna and power supply installed at the Valdilecha-CEMEX's secondary.

After writing D4.3, these last issues were resolved, so the status of this service integration and implementation is as follows (the related pictures are appended below):

- The antenna is placed in a higher position to have greater coverage thanks to the 25-meter cables purchased.
- The camera is adjusted, and the aluminium profile was cut to prevent it from protruding.
- The sailcloth over the conveyor belt is expanded to prevent the entry of dirt and control the light.

Figure 58: Final installation of grain size determination service equipment.

To validate the hardware at the quarry and installation, several on-site testing have been done to adjust the camera location and settings (exposure time, frame rate, gain, gamma, white balance, region of interest, etc.) using its camera viewer.

Figure 59: Camera viewer with an image received from 4/20 camera (left) and sample of captured image (right) at the Valdilecha-CEMEX's secondary.

Following the same considerations explained in the quality service, communications and service monitoring modules have been developed to enable remote access using OpenVPN network, communicate the computer vision system with other elements, and sending data using 3G or 4G via the IoT network and platform of Telefonica. Therefore, when the PC with the attached 4G modem is turned on, the communication module starts, and acquisition software waits for the modem connection to run the VPN. In this case, an interface module to display the image taken by the camera is not needed because there is no operator working in that crusher booth.

The image acquisition software has been developed using the SDK provided by the camera vendor and developed following the same considerations explained in quality service. To create a dataset, currently the images are sending to the Sigma servers to train a model. Once the Computer Vision model is deployed at the quarry, this data will not be sent unless a refined dataset is required.

5.3.2 Data integration in the IQS

This service aims at identifying every grain that is visible from the top view of a conveyor belt to generate a representative distribution of sizes that provides reliable information about the granulometry of the material. To obtain it, a segmentation algorithm is applied to the pre-processed images to obtain the particle contour. Subsequently the pixel areas of fragments are collected and, from them, the particle size distribution of the given image is generated. Finally, relevant information about the predicted particle size distribution is extracted in a json file daily (% of material considering different size

measures methods, number of instances, sieves, ...) as the output of the granulometry service. Currently, several measures methods are considered (area, major axis of the best-fit oriented rectangle and minor axis of the best-fit oriented rectangle) for each label (intervals that each datapoint represents based on sieves). This information is given based on the number of instances for each label (integer format, for example bins_Area=190) or based on the percentage used in the granulometric curves (float format, for example Area% = 30.4). The output json file is sent from the quarry using 3-4G networking (a modem and a SIM are integrated on the local PC) throughput provided by the Movistar Spanish IOT network. Samples of the proposed data integration scheme in the IQS and daily json file from the computer vision system are shown below.

Figure 60: Scheme about the grain size determination service results integration in the IQS.

```

{
  "Timestamp": "2024-05-28T09:46:12.381572",
  "ORMaxSize%": [0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 4.0, 7.0, 15.3, 16.8, 34.5, 34.5, 34.7, 69.6, 80.0, 85.0, 99.3, 100.0, 100.0, 100.0],
  "ORMinSize%": [0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 4.0, 7.0, 15.3, 16.8, 34.5, 34.5, 34.7, 69.6, 80.0, 85.0, 99.3, 100.0, 100.0, 100.0],
  "Area%": [0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 4.0, 7.0, 15.3, 16.8, 34.5, 34.5, 34.7, 69.6, 80.0, 85.0, 99.3, 100.0, 100.0, 100.0],
  "bins_ORMaxSize": [0, 0, 0, 40, 70, 153, 128, 345, 345, 347, 696, 800, 850, 93, 0, 0, 0],
  "bins_ORMinSize": [0, 0, 0, 40, 70, 153, 128, 345, 345, 347, 696, 800, 850, 93, 0, 0, 0],
  "bins_Area": [0, 0, 0, 40, 70, 153, 128, 345, 345, 347, 696, 800, 850, 93, 0, 0, 0],
  "labels": ["(0.0, 0.063]", "(0.063, 0.125]", "(0.125, 0.25]", "(0.25, 0.5]", "(0.5, 1]", "(1, 2]", "(2, 4]", "(4, 6]", "(6, 8]", "(8, 10]", "(10, 12.5]", "(12.5, 16]"]
}

```

Figure 61: A sample daily json file from the C33 conveyor belt camera (4/20mm material) computer vision system (dummy values)

Again, the output of the granulometry service is uploaded to the IQS following a process identical to the one described in the quality determination service (section 4.2.2). Whenever a new output is generated, a script is called to generate the metadata file, create the zip file and send it to the Data Lake. From there, it reaches the Data Warehouse by a pipeline, structured according to the table presented in section 6.4.

5.3.3 Service outputs

The grain size determination service will provide the predicted size of the particles in aggregates to monitor whether the material of the conveyor belt C33 meets technical specifications of the 4/20mm silo at Valdilecha-CEMEX quarry. The images below show a preliminary version of the PowerBI dashboard. The alarm dashboard is shared with the quality determination service.

Figure 62. Grain size determination dashboard with selected date.

5.4 Stockpile volume calculation service integration at HOLCIM and VICAT

5.4.1 Service integration and deployment

As introduced in deliverable D4.3, the service aims to integrate visual and data inputs to estimate the volume of the different piles to keep track of the stock available in the quarry and thus of the production. This information and the historical data shall aid operators, managers, and other AI services in optimizing plant production and multiple other scenarios, mainly focused on the following aspects: Resource Management, Safety and Compliance, and Predictive Analysis.

This service was initially conceived using fixed position cameras, but due to the number of stockpiles within a quarry and the need for a minimum of 3 cameras per pile, the investment costs would be high and difficult to maintain due to changes in the configuration of the stockpile positioning or slight deviations of the camera positioning due to external factors (Meteorological conditions, unforeseen events like mechanical shocks, etc.). Therefore, it was decided to develop an App for smartphones to capture stockpile videos, facilitating the operation of the service and allowing the quarry owners to use it for as much as stockpiles available on their sites.

With this approach, the service calculates the volume of the piles using one of three data sources, resulting in three different technological approaches: drone flights, ground multi-view images (multipoint smartphone data), and satellite imagery.

5.4.1.1 Drone flights and satellite images as a testing and evaluation tool

In order to validate the mobile app approach, the UPM-AI team also incorporated a test procedure using in the one hand their own drone and related software and on the other satellite images captured by ESA to calculate with different approaches the same stockpile volumes considered during the design of the mobile app approach processing sw framework. The drone technology is a mature technology and is a valid approach to corroborate the accuracy of the

solution designed with the mobile. For the satellite images similar image processing technologies are employed as the ones used for drones.

5.4.1.2 Mobile application video capture deployment components

The application being developed to capture stockpiles videos using a smartphone involves two main components. Each of them is described below:

5.4.1.2.1 Back-end

The back-end for this AI service involves a series of proprietary Python modules from UPM-AI to manage the data, to process (pre- and post-processing as well) it (segment, split, clean, precompute poses and geo-references...), communicate with the DEQ platform, and upload results. For the 3D reconstruction and volume calculation pipeline, we use OpenSfm and COLMAP.

OpenSfm is an open-source Python library that implements state-of-the-art Structure from Motion (SfM) and Multi-View Stereo (MVS) techniques, including 3D camera pose estimation and correction based on motion.

COLMAP follows a similar approach using an optimized data management approach to speed up computations. The rest of the process is covered using proprietary modules developed by the AI team to filter out, pre- and post-process the data, segment piles, geo-reference the models, and benchmark the results from the different approaches.

In addition to the processing pipeline module, the back-end:

1. Merges results and metadata.
2. Monitors the service, including health checks on all its components.
3. Manages the data, keeps control and track of its operations, and stores the input data.
4. Export the results.

5.4.1.2.2 Mobile application for image capturing components

The initial approach for the smartphone data acquisition involves two Android open-source GNU APPs for geo-referenced video acquisition (OpenCamera) and sensor logging (SensorLogger). These apps cover all data acquisition needs but do not include back-end or DEQ data platform data-sharing capabilities. These open-source APPs provide:

- A valid approach for collecting images and video samples during the approach validation process.
- Fine-tuning the video footage acquisition guidelines.
- First tests and input acquisition, geometry reconstruction, and volume estimation.

Additionally, during preliminary tests for validation with the HOLCIM team using controlled versions of these apps on Android 10 to 13 and different smartphones, it was found that SensorLogger APP crashed. For this reason, an alternative approach was developed as a temporal solution based on OpenCamera only. Due to this change, no pose information is collected, and the processing time increased significantly, though still satisfying the service requirements. As mentioned, we can use models such as MENet for pose estimation with promising results.

Subsequently, these APPs should be substituted by a single APP that includes geo-referenced video acquisition and sensor logging simultaneously, automatically uploading collected data to the back-end.

5.4.1.3 Video stockpile volume processing backend

Videos captured by the methods described above are processed on a dedicated server, which is not physically located on-site. This server receives the videos of the stock piles following the strategy described in D4.3:

1. For drone flights, video footage will be uploaded directly to a server to process the data once the scheduled flights are completed. A specific front-end should be ready to upload this data without directly interacting with the data and processing infrastructure.

2. For fixed cameras, snapshots or videos can be also gathered at controlled moments, and data will be sent from the quarry using 3G or 4G networking (similar to the "Quality Determination" and "Grain Size Determination" services).
3. The videos collected by the smartphone approach and components are also sent to the backend. The mobile APP will ease this operation integrating data acquisition and backend uploading needs.
4. For the satellite imagery approach, contrary to the previous capturing technologies, the solution is based on data acquisition for an external data source upon request, and the results are directly uploaded to the Data Lake. Data inputs are not uploaded to the DEQ data platform due to the massive images involved in this service (several Gigabytes per geo-referenced image file, GeoTIFF).

5.4.2 Data integration in the IQS

The strategy to upload data to the IQS is similar to the one followed in the quality and granulometry services. The information produced by the service (the volume of the stockpiles, along with other metadata) after processing the videos is sent to the Data Lake using the CDMP proxy. As in the previous cases, whenever the processing server generates an output, the information is zipped into an archive, together with the metadata file, and sent to the Data Lake. From there, it is extracted, aggregated and stored in the Data Warehouse, following the process described in section 5.2.2.

5.4.3 Service outputs

The service will generate information for all the piles that are captured within a quarry. This information includes the date of the measurement, the volume estimation and the error of said estimation. The image below presents the dashboard that will show the service output:

Figure 63. Volume calculation service's dashboard

The dashboard will also include the time since the previous measurement and allow to compare the results with the average pile volume. Besides, the dashboard will include a historical view of the volume measurements, allowing to focus on a certain pile or piles. The following image shows the prototype of this dashboard:

Figure 64. Volume calculation service's dashboard. Historical view

5.5 Production and consumption forecast service integration and deployment at CIMPOR

5.5.1 Service integration and deployment

This service was initially conceived as a data driven service extracted from the available digitized data at CIMPOR. But, unfortunately, some key data could not be obtained in an automatic way with the periodicity needed. Therefore, it was decided to install and design specific sensors to get important data such as: Dust levels, water consumption and meteorological data from the quarry itself.

In D4.1 the installation and deployment were already described and for the sake of clarity the relevant content is copied here.

As mentioned before, the Forecast service makes use of the quarry's operational data and information from external sources to feed AI algorithms. These data are gathered by DEQ's IQS and made available to the service by the Data Warehouse. The Forecast service retrieves this information and stores it locally and provides it to the corresponding module. Once processed, it is stored back into the DWH, to be visualized from the PowerBI dashboard:

Figure 65: Forecast service architecture.

5.5.1.1 Hardware components

Although in principle this service considered no hardware components, due to the lack of available data about dust, it was decided to complement the service with a dust level monitoring system.

This system consists of four air quality monitors connected to a gateway, communicating over the LoRaWAN technology:

Figure 66: Dust monitoring system architecture.

As mentioned, the dust sensors send data periodically over LoRa to the gateway, which, in turn, sends these data to a network server provided by The Things Network. The LoRa technology (along with its communication protocol, LoRaWAN) is a long-range communication technique, frequently used in IoT applications due mainly to its low consumption. The network server provides a way to manage and centralize the data gathered by one or more gateways, receiving data over the internet. Lastly, the data is sent from the network server to the DEQ’s IoT platform, to be ultimately stored in the Data Lake together with other CIMPOR data.

The following components have been used to implement the system:

5.5.1.2 LoRa Gateway:

The gateway must be able to receive the LoRa messages from the sensors and to communicate with the network server. Since no wired or wireless network will probably be available in the quarry, cellular connectivity is also required. For this purpose, the Dragino LoRa Outdoor Gateway was selected:

Figure 67: LoRa gateway.

The gateway allows for Ethernet, WiFi, 3G or 4G communications, and can be powered by 12V PoE. It is also built with outdoors deployment in mind, making it suitable for the quarry.

5.5.1.3 Dust sensors

To monitor the dust levels, it was decided to deploy four air quality sensors, to have information about the dust in different points of the quarry. Two types of sensors have been used:

5.5.1.3.1 Industrial Air Quality Monitor:

To have a baseline to compare the custom-made sensors explained in the next section, the Enginko MCF-LW12TERPM Air Quality Monitor was acquired.

This device can gather information about air particulate matter, as well as temperature and humidity, in outdoors environments. It is powered by a battery, which can be recharged by solar energy.

Figure 68: Industrial Air Quality Monitor.

5.5.1.3.2 Custom-made Air Quality Sensors:

In order to minimize the cost of the system, it was decided to develop the remaining three dust sensors using off-the-shelf components. The final sensor is shown below.

Figure 69: Final version of the Sigma-made dust sensors

5.5.1.4 Pulse counter sensors for water monitoring

To have an accurate reading of water usage in the quarry, it was decided to install a water consumption system. Since two water flow meters with pulse output are available in CIMPOR Alenquer's water tank, a LoRaWAN pulse counter sensor was installed in each of them. These sensors simply count the pulses that the flow meter outputs (one pulse every 10 liters) and send these readings to the LoRa gateway.

The chosen model was the Milesight EM300, which has native integration to the existing LoRa infrastructure and can be powered by a battery for up to 5 years.

Figure 70. Milesight EM300 LoRa Pulse Counter

5.5.1.5 Wind sensor

Even though wind information can be obtained from the Portuguese weather service, the distance from the closes weather station to the quarry makes this information not as accurate as desired. Thus, it was decided to complement the sensor system with an anemometer. As the other sensors, the anemometer is also LoRa-based, so integrating it with the rest of the infrastructure is straight forward. The chosen model was the RAK Wireless Sensor Hub, together with the Wind probe, as shown in the picture below. Due to an issue with the received unit, the deployment of this sensor had to be delayed.

Figure 71. Wind sensor for CIMPOR Alenquer quarry.

5.5.1.6 Deployment of the hardware components at the CIMPOR pilot

Thanks to the great collaboration of CIMPOR, a plan to cover with the sensors most of that exploitation area of the quarry was drawn. Meaning that the separation of the sensors had to be considerable, but the line of sight has to be assured with the LORA gateway in order to guarantee the communication between all the sensors and the gateway.

Another important requirement was that power supply had to be available for the Gateway. All the other sensor components are running with batteries and in the case of the dust sensors, a solar panel was included in the design, to provide self-charging capabilities.

The deployment map (Google map) is here below appended showing the distribution of the components around the pilot area.

Figure 72. CIMPOR pilot sensor network deployment map

5.5.2 Data integration in the IQS

The gateway sends the data it receives to the sensors to the Data Lake. The DL Browser is the component that processes and stores this data. From there, a *pipeline* is set up to extract this data, aggregate and add it to the Data Warehouse. At this point, data is available for direct visualizations, such as the dust levels or the current water consumption.

Furthermore, the Forecast components extract these data, (along with other information contained in the DWH, such as About's truck traffic data) to feed the models that will estimate the water, production and energy models, storing the results back in the Data Warehouse, as shown in Figure 16.

An in-depth description of this process can be found in section 3 of deliverable D4.4.

5.5.3 Service outputs

The outputs of the Forecast service are classified in three different groups, according to the main goals of the service: water consumption minimization, production optimization and clean energy usage.

Water consumption:

On the one hand, this service will provide outputs to monitor the current status of the quarry in terms of dust, water usage and localized weather conditions (temperature, humidity and wind), which will be visualized in PowerBI dashboards. The image below shows a preliminary version of the dust and weather monitoring dashboard:

Figure 73. Dust and weather monitoring dashboard.

On the other hand, the service will provide a prediction of water usage at a certain date, taking into account the past usage as well as the dust conditions in the quarry. This information is displayed in the following dashboard, together with the water consumption history:

Water

Figure 74. Water monitoring dashboard for CIMPOR.

Production optimization:

The service will also provide an estimation of periods of time in which the production will be the highest, taking into account the past production history and the current and future weather conditions. This information is displayed in the following dashboard, where the left-hand graph represents the production history, and the right-hand graph, the impact in the production (compared to the theoretical maximum) for the upcoming days:

Production

Figure 75. Production optimization dashboard for CIMPOR.

Clean energy usage:

Lastly, the service will provide an indication of when the energy available is originated from renewable sources, so that production can be concentrated in those periods. This output will be derived from the energy prices in Spain and Portugal and the weather predictions. As before, this information is displayed in the following dashboard:

Figure 76. Clean energy usage dashboard for CIMPOR.

5.6 Anomalies detection service integration and deployment at CSI

5.6.1 Service integration and deployment

As presented in deliverable D4.3, this service aims at using aerial and contact sensors to monitor the production line at the quarry site constantly. Continuous monitoring of the different lines and components should ease the detection of malfunctions or failures of the machinery and minimize their impact on production. Ultimately, this may be used to develop predictive maintenance capabilities using external metadata on the individual parts involved.

The service uses a relatively small intelligent capturing device with a microprocessor and various sensors, in particular microphones and vibration sensors to monitor a given quarry plant component (conveyor belt, crusher, sieve, etc...) and collect data that are being processed by AI models to characterize the equipment under test and detect possible failures.

5.6.1.1 Data Capturing device deployment

As mentioned, the service requires a specific hardware component to capture noise and vibrations at the production line of a quarry, to monitor the functioning of specific equipment, and generate functioning profiles and alarms. Deliverable D4.3 introduced the architecture of this device, based on a Raspberry Pi:

Figure 77. Hardware of the deployed sensors and schematic on the main software components focusing on control.

This device needs to be placed in the proximity of the device under test with access to an AC power connection outlet. And for data communication purposes, a VPN has to be deployed using for example a WIFI network as needed by CSI where the service is being deployed.

5.6.1.2 Software deployed components

According to the service architecture, the SW for this service involves two separate parts corresponding to the edge-cloud paradigm. Each of them is described below separately. One should note that specific audio processing capabilities are replicated on both sides, as well as communications. The cloud side operates the heavy computations (learning, modelling, classification, etc.). In contrast, the edge side focuses on low, rapid computations for continuously monitoring input streams (pre-processing, AI triggers, etc.). Thus, complex algorithmics shall be avoided on the latter, focusing on online processing, while the former may address the more complex and offline processes.

5.6.1.2.1 Edge

At the quarry. Input streams (audio and vibration) are digitally filtered and adapted to mitigate the impact of spurious background effects. At the same time, fixed-duration signal chunks are extracted to evaluate AI triggers based on time-frequency representations. This is a standard processing pipeline for any 1-dimensional signal.

The AI triggers are based on light AI models that evaluate a given event's likelihood instead of standard triggers (e.g., single or double directional edges, intervals, logic, counters, etc.). For this project, we use unsupervised models trained on time-frequency audio representations, avoiding the need for energy- and time-consuming computations. The edge module manages the models while they are trained and uploaded from the cloud. Multiple models can be used simultaneously and stored within the edge components. The command and control and service monitoring components handle execution control and monitoring.

Depending on the result of the trigger, the system may extract the audio from the original sample and the compact triggering representation and share it with the DEQ data platform and the cloud back-end. This may happen in arbitrary situations, to collect probes to calibrate the system and monitor it, or when a trigger condition is met.

If a trigger condition is met, different pieces of information should be sent to the agents involved. The module shall:

- Fire an alarm to the alarm dashboard system (installed at the quarry).
- Send an abnormal event to the DEQ data platform, including the type of event, timestamp, module/site unique identifier, and the corresponding raw signal to ease posterior processing. Note that for this task, a minimum delay may exist for the signalled alarm due to signal windowing and overlaps.
- Send the data to the cloud module for storing and posterior evaluation of the sample using more advanced (and computationally heavier) models.

Finally, the edge component must include minimum necessary functionalities to monitor its service, connectivity, health, etc., and allow full remote command and control. Regarding communications, the edge component is intended to include different RF front-ends, typically Wi-Fi, 3G, and 4G, and a physical connection through Ethernet RJ45. The processor Linux-based operating system (Debian, final version to be defined) manages all these interfaces seamlessly for the rest of the components.

5.6.1.2.2 Cloud

Service back-end. This component is meant to communicate with all deployed edge modules from the different quarry sites and to:

1. Merge results and metadata.
2. Monitor the service, including health checks on all its components.
3. Monitor and control the learning process and model deployment on the edge components.
4. Orchestrate operations among all edge components.

5. Manage data, control and track operations, and store the extracted input data.
6. Export results to the DEQ data infrastructure.

Modules (1), (4), (5), and (6) are proprietary and developed specifically for the DEQ project. For (2), we use standard Python libraries and open-source projects, including Sentry, Traefik, and Graphite. For (3), we use open-source TensorBoard, while the programming of the AI models uses PyTorch.

5.6.2 Data integration in the IQS

The output generated by the service is integrated in the IQS with a process identical to that of the granulometry, quality and volume calculation services. In this case, the detected anomalies, together with other metadata, are zipped and sent to the Data Lake, and then to the Data Warehouse, according to the process described in section 5.2.2.

5.6.3 Service outputs

As before, the outputs of the anomalies detection service will be displayed in a Power BI dashboard. In this case, the dashboard will present the number of detected alarms and the latest one, along with the time passed since the last detection. It is also planned to include an indication of the status of the sensors, such as a keep-alive message. The prototype of this dashboard is shown below:

Figure 78. Anomalies detection service's dashboard.

In addition, the dashboard will also present the history of detected alarms, allowing users to filter by a certain location to visualize all events in a certain period. The image below shows said dashboard:

Figure 79. Anomalies detection service's dashboard. Historical view

5.7 MetaQuarry service integration for HOLCIM and VICAT

5.7.1 Service integration and Deployment

For the Metaquarry service pilot it is important to highlight that it is a web service that runs on Sigma's computing infrastructure featuring three different main components: a Web Application, a Natural Language Processing API and a search engine as explained in D4.3. The architecture is here below appended.

Figure 80. Metaquarry service architecture

With respect to the deployment architecture, Sigma has introduced the possibility of a very flexible deployment infrastructure with respect to the database of documentation that could be processed upon. Below a diagram of this deployment infrastructure is attached.

Figure 81. Flexible Metaquarry deployment architecture

The document library that is analyzed by Metaquarry can be implemented in the following 4 different environments:

- The user can use a Microsoft sharepoint infrastructure available at its premises. This configuration is simple and in principle there is no need of adapting somehow the structure of the document base.
- A similar possibility as above is being integrated. This time with a google drive cloud infrastructure. Metaquarry will be able to connect to the customer google document database if available.
- In case of no document management infrastructure, only storage capabilities in the customer premises, a possibility of using a private cloud to handle all needed documentation is possible via the Owncloud¹⁰ commercial service.
- Finally a possibility to connect Metaquarry to the DEQ Datalake was studied, but due to the access characteristics, having to deal with the CDMP commands, makes this possibility not as flexible as the ones described above. The document indexing over Datalake is significantly less efficient as for the other cases. Then in this specific case, it is recommended to go for the above described options.

Finally it is important to highlight that for each one of the pilots using Metaquarry: VICAT and HOLCIM, a specific interface was tuned for each one of them (example queries), and also the native language use: French and Italian respectively. In fact, now in Metaquarry all project's languages (Spanish, French, German, Italian, etc...) are already incorporated in the LLM used.

5.7.2 Service outputs

With respect to the outputs of the service, here below a set of screenshots for the HOLCIM Metaquarry instantiation are appended in the table below with a short explanation of the functionalities.

¹⁰ <https://owncloud.com>

Table 8. Metaquarry output for the HOLCIM instantiation

Interface screenshots	Explanation																																																																																												
	<p>Here we see the main page of the service after entering the credentials. A set of example questions can be used as shown in the picture, in Italian or English.</p>																																																																																												
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	<p>Now, the result of a query is shown. It is important to mention that Metaquarry comes up with an answer in green, with the best fit to the query that is processed. The language used here is Italian.</p> <p>Moreover a list of documents is displayed that feature the most probable answer to the query.</p> <p>The document can be downloaded or can be browsed directly on the navigator by clicking on the document icon.</p>	
	<p>Similar result as above but this time in English.</p>	

6 Data warehouse integration and deployment

6.1 Introduction

As introduced in deliverable D4.4, the Data Warehouse is a component in the IQS that is focused on storing historical data related to business intelligence, obtaining these data from the Data Lake and other sources. Having such component allows to conduct business analysis to unveil relationships amongst variables that otherwise would remain hidden.

As already known, the Google BigQuery solution is being used. To understand the functionalities that make BigQuery, an architecture diagram is presented below.

BigQuery is a good option for data analysis driven to answer to business needs, rapidly, with less data operations and many analysis tools at your disposal that are constantly updated and provide state of the art tools, including AI models.

*source: Google/BigQuery

Figure 82. BigQuery architecture

From the above picture it is important to understand that BigQuery separates clearly data storage and data processing in a very optimized way, allowing the latter to rapidly analyze and access your data, using SQL or advanced programming routines including AI models.

6.2 Architecture revisited

The architecture of the DWH has not gone through many changes since the one presented in D4.4. The Data Warehouse retrieves quarry data from the Data Lake (through the CDMP and DL Browser) and other data from external sources. The main addition is the inclusion of data from a weather station located nearby CIMPOR-Alenquer’s quarry and managed by its municipality. These data are used in the Forecast service.

The image below shows the up-to-date architecture:

Figure 83. DWH Architecture update

6.3 Interfaces

The Data Warehouse interacts with different components, for data insertion and extraction. These interfaces are detailed below.

6.3.1 Data lake

The main source of data is the Data Lake component. The DL provides two main tools to access its data: the CDMP and the DL browser. The latter allows to interact with the data gathered by sensors (such as the ones deployed in CIMPOR Alenquer quarry), while the former gives access to the remaining data.

Although, at this stage of the project, more data is available in the Data Lake (e.g. data from water sensors, output of video services), the way of accessing these data has not changed from the one reported in deliverable D4.4. These new data are reflected, though, in the tables that have to be created to organize this information, and that are explained in section 6.4.

6.3.2 Power BI

PowerBI is the main visualization tool used in the project. Thanks to its native integration with BigQuery, data stored in the DWH is easily available in PowerBI. BigQuery allows to define per-table permissions, so a PowerBI user will only be able to see data for which they have been granted access rights. The image below shows part of the data imported in PowerBI:

Figure 84. PowerBI's data model

More information about how to use PowerBI to access DWH data can be found in the *Usage* section of deliverable D4.4.

6.3.3 External Services

As shown in Figure 28, the Data Warehouse also extracts from external sources to complement the information obtained from the Data Lake. At this stage, three external sources are being integrated: weather data for Portugal, electricity prices for Spain and Portugal and localized weather data from a station nearby the CIMPOR Alenquer quarry.

Weather data for Portugal (IPMA):

This information is used by the Forecast service, to feed the production and energy models. As explained in D4.4, the weather data is publicly available through the IPMA's (Instituto Português do Mar e da Atmosfera) API:

<https://api.ipma.pt/open-data/observation/meteorology/stations/observations.json>

A data pipeline is set up to make a call to this API, process the response and store it in the Data Warehouse, a process that is configured to occur once per day.

Electricity prices for Spain and Portugal (OMIE):

This information is also used by the Forecast service to feed the energy consumption model. In this case, the information is retrieved from OMIE, the nominated electricity market operator (NEMO) for the Iberian Peninsula. As before, the energy prices are publicly available through OMIE's API:

[https://www.omie.es/es/file-download?parents\[0\]=marginalpdbc&filename=marginalpdbc_\[YYYYMMDD\].1](https://www.omie.es/es/file-download?parents[0]=marginalpdbc&filename=marginalpdbc_[YYYYMMDD].1)

Where the last part of the URL between brackets indicates the date of the data that will be downloaded. As before, a data pipeline is configured to be triggered once per day, retrieving the electricity prices in CSV format, processing it and storing it the Data Warehouse.

6.4 Tables

As mentioned in D4.4, data in a DWH needs to be structured in tables, to make the process of building queries to display the data as easy as possible. New tables have been created to account for the added data, following the table design process described in D4.4:

Wind information:

These tables store the information produced by the weather station installed in CIMPOR Alenquer. The station provides wind speed and direction, together with temperature, humidity and pressure:

Wind	
datetime	date
float	wind_direction
float	wind_speed
float	temperature
float	humidity
float	pressure

Figure 85. Weather station tables

Water optimization:

These tables store the information produced by the pulse counters that are connected to the water meters installed in CIMPOR Alenquer, together with the output of the water optimization algorithm.

water_consumption_projections	
datetime	projection_date
datetime	projected_date
float	projection_value

water_consumption_measures	
datetime	update_date
string	sensor
datetime	measure_date
float	measure_value

water_consumption_insights	
	insight_date
	generated_image

Figure 86. Water optimization tables

Quality and granulometry services:

These tables store the information generated by the quality and grain size services:

- **Quality:** the output of the quality service contains the amount of clay and limestone in each sample (in percentage and in number of pixels), as well as the colour of each material in different colour spaces (RGB and Munsell):

Quality	
datetime	timestamp
float	background_percentage
float	material_percentage
float	clay_percentage
float	limestone_percentage
int	total_px
int	clay_px
string	clay_mean_rgb
string	limestone_mean_rgb
string	clay_munsell
string	limestone_munsell

Figure 87. Quality service table

- **Granulometry:** the granulometry service returns the amount of material in each size range of the 4/20 material (these size ranges are represented by *bins* in the table below), calculated using different methods, such as best fit rectangle or inscribed circumference:

Granulometry	
datetime	timestamp
string	method
int	bin1
int	bin2
int	bin4
int	bin8
int	bin10
int	bin16
int	bin20
int	bin32
int	bin40

Figure 88. Granulometry service table

7 BIM

In contemporary project management, the concept of a Common Data Environment (CDE) has gained significant traction. A CDE can be defined as a single source of information for a project, providing a common platform for all stakeholders to access, edit, and manage critical project data. In essence, it functions as a central repository for project information, documents, and communications, facilitating collaboration and enhancing project efficiency.

In the context of DigiEcoQuarry, we recognized the pivotal role that a model-based CDE could play in connecting Building Information Modeling (BIM) models with real-time data provided by other project partners. This integration presented an invaluable opportunity to streamline project management processes. By integrating data from various sources, such as sensors, equipment, and relevant data about its treatment plant assets, the system facilitates a deeper understanding of the quarry's processes and performance. By providing a detailed and dynamic digital replica of the quarry, the adoption of a model-based CDE enhances the visualization of project data, streamlines decision-making processes, enhances operational efficiency, and promotes a proactive approach to maintenance and resource management.

7.1 3D Model Integration

To initiate work in the proposed CDE Environment, we uploaded the Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) models to Autodesk Tandem. This process ensured the inclusion of essential components such as quarry assets, mobile machinery, and stockpiles, tailored to the specific requirements of the designated pilot site and based on the available information from other project partners.

In the 4D BIM Planning process, a critical aspect is the accurate development of model assets, where each element is modelled as a distinct and identifiable asset to enable its association with related data. Consequently, some of the pilot site models required modification to meet this criterion. It is important to note that the requirements for 4D BIM Planning and a CDE System can differ significantly, necessitating the use of the most efficient model for each system.

For example, the 4D BIM Planning might require the display of material volumes, roads, and mobile machinery, which are not needed in the CDE system. Conversely, the CDE system might require stockpiles, which are not necessary for the 4D BIM Planning tool, where all terrain and material elements are integrated.

Figure 89 : Valdilecha-CEMEX Model for CDE Implementation

Figure 90: Valdilecha-CEMEX Model for 4D BIM Planning.

7.2 Quarry Assets Integration

In the development of our model-based Common Data Environment (CDE), it was crucial to ensure that the CDE was practical and effective. This required integrating all relevant information from each element into the model and establishing connections to external data for each related element. To achieve this, it was essential to clearly identify each element within the model.

We accomplished this by using the same coding system employed in the pilot site's data, ensuring clarity for their respective teams. Each element was assigned a unique identification (ID). We then incorporated all the static data associated with each element, including manufacturer details, model specifications, motor type, maintenance schedules, and documents related to its mechanical parts, sensors, or manufacturers. This approach allows users to access a comprehensive view of all properties linked to a specific element and its associated documentation with a single click, simplifying document management significantly.

Figure 59. CDE: 3D Model Element related static data.

7.3 Quarry Digital Twins & Data Dashboards

Upon the establishment of the model-based Common Data Environment (CDE), we seamlessly integrated the daily data from the WP3 partners and the pilot site into the system, thereby transforming it into a dynamic live Digital Twin. The incorporation of data varied depending on the specific site and the available information. Some data were related to the usage of mobile machinery, while others pertained to production and consumption data, and so forth.

By linking the 3D models with the real-time data, we enabled the visualization of all the data associated with each element by simply clicking on it. This includes accessing the latest data as well as reviewing historical data through comprehensive charts that illustrate an element’s behaviour over a specific period. This functionality empowers the quarry team to identify any anomalies or changes that require close monitoring.

Figure 60. CDE as a Digital Twin. Connection with external data.

7.3.1 Data Integration with Data Lake

In the context of the Common Data Environment (CDE), the integration of data from Work Package 3 (WP3) partners is facilitated through an integration to the Data Lake. In this process, assuming DEQ partners upload their respective data into the Data Lake utilizing their preferred methods and timeframes, an internally developed integrator interacts with the Data Lake API, extracting data at regular intervals of every 12 hours. It’s important to note, that for future implementations, the integrator is able to interact with the Data Lake at much shorter intervals of time (we estimate that anything from 1 hour intervals would be cautious), but because of the data currently available in the Data Lake and the frequency of its updates, it was concluded that 12 hours intervals were more than enough to keep the system up-to-date.

This extracted data is then channelled into the BIM CDE expert system, enabling the consumption of relevant information and fostering collaborative data utilization within the framework of the CDE.

Figure 62. Data Integration Process.

8 Conclusions

This document, D4.6: "Report on IQS Services Integration and Deployment," is a public deliverable created within the framework of WP4. It provides a final report on the implemented digital solutions and details how all the building blocks have been integrated and deployed. This deliverable completes the description of WP4's work and updates the following documents where necessary:

- D1.3: Requirements for Quarry Full Digitalization (for Smart Sensors, Automation & Process Control, and for ICT Solutions, BIM and AI report)
- D4.1: Report on IQS ICT Requirement Analysis
- D4.2: Report on IQS Design and Architecture
- D4.4: Report on Architecture of the Data Warehouse and Its Integration
- D4.5: BIM - Planning 4D for All the Pilots

The implementation of digital solutions reported in chapter 3 and chapter 4 of the IQS involves the development and integration of several building blocks. These building blocks include Data Lakes for data management and storage on Azure cloud, an Application Gateway for exposing REST API web services, Keycloak for user authentication and authorization, and Microservices tailored to specific quarry process. Additionally, Talend is used as an integration platform, while Azure Data Storage and PostgreSQL serve as the storage solutions. All these building blocks are integrated into the Centralized Data Management Platform (CDMP), which serves as a central hub for data management, data sharing and collaboration among quarry partners.

The interfaces of the IQS with external expert systems through proxy patterns, ensure seamless data exchange and integration with various systems such as the Metso Mobile Crusher System, Roctim Simulation Platform, Maestro Automation & SCADA Systems, Abaut Analytics System, DH&P Transport System, Sandvik Drilling Report system and more. This integration demonstrates the efficiency of the IQS in managing and utilizing quarry data, which was greatly facilitated by the definition of data models and common data formats.

Furthermore, the IQS leverages the Power BI ecosystem to provide comprehensive visualization and reporting capabilities for KPIs across different aspects of quarry operations. This seamless integration demonstrates the IQS's capability to break down data silos and enable efficient data management, ultimately contributing to improved decision-making and performance tracking.

The platform has been enriched by the addition of InfluxDB (Tick Stack) and Grafana. These components will enhance the platform's capabilities to utilize new time-series data formats, perform exploratory analysis of raw data, and create more sophisticated visualizations (dashboards). Initial experiments with DHP raw data demonstrate the effectiveness of such a solution.

Regarding the AI Services, their deployment has progressed for all of them: models have been refined to improve their results, new hardware sensors have been installed to increase the amount of available data, integration with the IQS has been achieved or planned, and the outputs have been defined, as well as the dashboards that will display these outputs. Work on the Data Warehouse has also advanced, with the creation of the necessary tables that store the AI Services outputs.

Finally for the BIM, the integration of a model-based Common Data Environment (CDE) within the DigiEcoQuarry project has shown the capabilities in enhancing project management and operational efficiency. By connecting Building Information Modeling (BIM) models with real-time data from various sources, the CDE provides a dynamic digital representation of the quarry. This integration facilitates better decision-making, improved visualization of project data, and a proactive approach to maintenance. Additionally, the seamless data integration with the Data Lake ensures that the CDE remains up-to-date, enabling comprehensive access to relevant information for all stakeholders. Ultimately, the implementation of a CDE fosters collaboration, streamlines processes, and supports the sustainable management of quarry operations.

References

- D1.3: Requirements for Quarry full digitalization (for Smart Sensors, Automation & Process Control, and for ICT solutions, BIM and AI report)
- D4.1: Report on IQS ICT requirement analysis.
- D4.2: Report on IQS design and architecture
- D4.4: Report on Architecture of the Data Warehouse and its integration.
- D4.5: BIM- Planning 4D for all the pilots.
- D5.4: Pre-verified Environmental Product Declaration documentation for pilot plant based on historical data.
- D7.1: Context narrative, social risk matrix and Stakeholder Mapping.
- D7.2: Social Risk Analysis

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